

Evaluating and selecting strategic alliance suppliers in reverse logistics using the ANP-TOPSIS hybrid method in a rough uncertainty environment

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Abstract

In recent years, the evolving domain of reverse logistics (RL) has garnered substantial attention for its role in facilitating companies to recognize potential resources while addressing the operational and strategic challenges associated with return processes. This research foregrounds the criticality of environmental sustainability and the optimization of these return processes within the supply chain, highlighting the significance of effective RL practices. It introduces an innovative methodology for evaluating and selecting strategic alliance suppliers in the RL domain, employing the ANP-TOPSIS hybrid method within a rough uncertainty environment. This approach is instrumental in navigating the complexities and inherent uncertainties of supplier selection, thus enhancing the efficiency and sustainability of RL operations.

By synthesizing the Analytic Network Process (ANP) to ascertain the relative importance of selection criteria, and the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) for ranking the suppliers—integrated within a rough set theory framework—the methodology adeptly addresses the multifaceted and interconnected criteria essential for strategic alliance supplier selection in RL. This includes considering both quantitative and qualitative data under uncertain conditions, thereby enabling the management of returned goods as a crucial segment in supply chain management.

The application of this method in the context of electronic waste recycling companies illustrates its dynamic capabilities in making informed decisions for supplier selection, demonstrating robustness and the potential to guide RL practitioners in developing sustainable, efficient, and resilient supply chain strategies. Moreover, establishing strategic alliances can streamline the return process, bring specialized expertise, ensure flexibility in dynamic markets, and contribute to cost savings, enhanced sustainability, improved risk management, and higher customer satisfaction levels.

This study not only enriches the reverse logistics literature by providing a structured and systematic approach to supplier selection, accommodating uncertainty, and complex interdependencies among criteria but also offers practical insights for industry professionals. It advances the academic understanding of RL supplier selection and underscores the multifaceted nature of RL and its potential to drive efficiency, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness across various industrial sectors.

Keywords: Reverse Logistics, Strategic Alliance, Supplier Selection, ANP-TOPSIS Hybrid Method, Rough Uncertainty Environment, Electronic Waste Recycling, Environmental Sustainability, Supply Chain Optimization, Rough WASPAS method

Chapter One
General Overview of the Research

Statement of the subject

Today, environmental protection and development are serious global issues. With the population growth and consumption of natural resources, the implementation of RL activities will soon become a "necessity" for many organizations. RL can achieve a proper balance between the economy and the environment, enabling companies to profit through preserving the value of second-hand goods and protecting the environment. However, RL is a critical issue in the closed-loop supply chain (Govindan and Soleimani, 2017). Supply chain management for RL mainly involves three aspects: products, suppliers, and raw materials. Among them, the evaluation and selection of suppliers is a significant strategic decision for reducing operational costs, enhancing company competitiveness, and developing more business opportunities (Yazdani et al., 2017; Mardani et al., 2020). Through RL, products are moved from their final destination to a new location where their value is considered and managed back into the production line or disposed of appropriately (Tavana et al., 2016).

In recent years, supplier selection has gradually become a valuable research topic in RL practice. The issues include how to select a Third-Party Reverse Logistics Provider (3PRLP) when manufacturers want to implement remanufacturing activities or appropriately perform recycling or disposal operations. The growing environmental responsiveness and forward-looking economic profitability have prompted more companies to outsource their logistic operations to S3PRLPs (Mavi et al., 2017; Li et al., 2018; Zarebkeshnia et al., 2018). For companies to achieve cost-saving and environmental sustainability goals, it's crucial to select the best S3PRLP option many factors encourage companies to implement RL, including stakeholders' environmental concerns, government regulations on RL, cost-effectiveness, sustainable development, etc., all contributing to a company's effective and efficient development (Prajapati et al., 2019). Currently, a company's supply chain performance is not only dependent on its performance but is also influenced by its partners' social and environmental performances. Any adverse consequences produced by other supply chain members can negatively impact the company (Da Silva et al., 2020). Thus, for companies involved in RL activities, whether aiming for better economic benefits or a social perspective, there's a pressing need for serious evaluation and selection of the suppliers they collaborate with increasing environmental concerns and potential economic profitability have pushed many manufacturers towards implementing RL. Due to the complexity of RL operations and resource constraints, outsourcing RL methods to a Third-Party Reverse Logistics Provider (3PRLP) is often favored. One of the most vital and riskiest processes in RL outsourcing is selecting the best 3PRLP from alternative options strategic alliances are a significant form of organizational cooperation that has been extensively covered in the literature. By forming strategic alliances, partners can synchronize their resources and strengths to achieve related objectives, share risks, acquire knowledge, and gain access to new markets. The term "strategic alliance" is used to describe an exchange relationship between two organizations aiming to create or acquire strategic resources choosing strategic partners in practice is complex due to the presence of various quantitative and qualitative criteria, relationships between these criteria, and various constraints such as budget, capacity, etc., making it a multi-criteria decision-making process. Given the importance of strategic partner selection and its impact on company performance, models for selecting strategic partners should be chosen that consider the relative importance and interchange between criteria selecting a 3PRLP is generally recognized as a High-Information Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (HI-MCDM) issue that involves multiple criteria that typically conflict with another criterion and are expressed in different information formats, for example, clear numbers, intervals, linguistic terms, and fuzzy numbers, to best preserve the original evaluation in a fuzzy environment. The psychological behavior of the decision-maker (DM) in making choices under environmental pressure has been proven to weigh heavily on the decision-making solution, but has not been

adequately considered in the existing literature. In response to this, the primary evaluation criteria in this research are examined based on Rough Interval Numbers (RIN) to be closer to the real world.

Research Necessity

The starting point of this research is the continuous enhancement of environmental protection awareness and the understanding of the concept of sustainable development in society. The recognition of the importance of reverse logistics in various industries is increasing year by year. Specifically, with stringent environmental regulations being implemented worldwide, supplier selection has become a crucial issue for companies. In response to the demand for logistical activities in the supply chain and to meet environmental compliance requirements, companies tend to choose RL suppliers who can best align with their demands and maximize both economic and environmental benefits.

Considering the rapid globalization of markets, the inefficiencies in the organic growth of organizations, the increasing environmental complexity, and the need to share knowledge and expertise, inter-organizational collaboration and strategic alliances have been identified as winning strategies for the growth and survival of organizations. Even many large companies, despite having a market monopoly, cannot avoid alliances with other firms. This is because the classic framework of strategic management might not adequately address the complexities of a turbulent technological environment and the constant advancements in innovations and fundamental structural changes.

On the other hand, the industrial sector has always been a significant factor in the economic progress and development of countries, and the primary concern of governments has been to support domestic manufacturing and service industries. The recycling of electronic waste plays a fundamental role and holds significant importance in organizations.

In recent years, the problem of electronic and electrical waste has posed serious challenges to the city of Tehran. Based on conducted studies, the production of electronic waste resulting from the disposal of digital electronic devices in developing countries has increased by about 40 million tons compared to the previous year. It is predicted that in the next 10 years (by 2026), the production of electronic waste in Tehran will increase tenfold. On the one hand, electronic wastes constitute 7% of the total waste volume, but unfortunately, these wastes account for 70% of the waste containing toxic substances. On the other hand, the amount of waste produced in Tehran is higher than in other major cities and capitals worldwide (Bakhtiari and Haji Zadeh, 2016).

Problem Statement

In recent years, Reverse Logistics (RL) has garnered increasing attention from researchers and industrialists. This is because it can manage the added value of End-of-Life (EOL) products through various product recovery processes such as reuse, separation, recycling, repair, and refurbishment. It also meets environmental requirements and emphasizes customer rights and benefits (Govindan et al., 2020).

Today, environmental protection and development are serious global issues. With population growth and the consumption of natural resources, the implementation of RL activities will soon become a "necessity" for many organizations. RL can achieve a proper balance between the economy and the environment, enabling companies to profit by preserving the value of second-

hand goods and protecting the environment. However, RL is a key issue in the closed-loop supply chain (Govindan and Salimani, 2017). Supply chain management for RL primarily involves three aspects: products, suppliers, and raw materials. Among them, evaluating and selecting suppliers is a crucial strategic decision for reducing operational costs, enhancing company competitiveness, and expanding more business opportunities (Yazdani et al., 2017; Mardani et al., 2020). Through RL, products are transferred from their final destination to a new location where their value is considered and either managed back into the production line or disposed of appropriately (Tavana et al., 2016).

In recent years, supplier selection has gradually become a valuable research issue in RL practice. Issues include how to choose a third-party reverse logistics provider (3PRLP) when manufacturers want to execute remanufacturing activities or appropriately conduct recycling or disposal operations. The growing responsiveness to environmental concerns and the potential economic profitability have driven many manufacturers towards RL. Due to the complexity of RL operations and the scarcity of resources, outsourcing RL methods to a third-party reverse logistics provider (3PRLP) is preferred. One of the most essential and riskiest processes for RL outsourcing is selecting the optimal 3PRLP from alternative options.

Strategic alliances are a significant form of organizational collaboration that has received extensive coverage in the literature. By forming a strategic alliance, partners can coordinate their resources and strengths to achieve related objectives, share risks, acquire knowledge, and gain access to new markets. The term "strategic alliance" is used to describe an exchange relationship between two organizations aiming to create or acquire strategic resources.

Choosing strategic partners in practice is a multi-criteria decision-making process due to various quantitative and qualitative criteria, relationships between these criteria, and various constraints such as budget and capacity. Given the importance of selecting strategic partners and their impact on company performance, models should be chosen for selecting strategic partners that consider the relative importance and trade-offs between criteria in the strategic partner selection process.

The selection of 3PRLP is generally recognized as a hybrid multi-criteria decision-making (HIMCDM) issue that involves multiple criteria, often conflicting with another criterion, and with different information formats, such as clear numbers, intervals, linguistic terms, and fuzzy numbers, to best preserve the primary evaluation in a fuzzy environment. The psychological behavior of the decision-maker (DM) in making choices under constant environmental pressure has been established to complicate the decision-making solution, but it has not been adequately considered in the existing literature. In response to this issue, the primary evaluation criteria in this research are examined based on rough interval numbers to be closer to the real world. Therefore, in this research, by taking advantage of a comprehensive literature review, the most critical indicators of reverse logistics supplier selection will be addressed, considering the strategic alliance.

The Necessity of Research

The modern world is witnessing a remarkable evolution in environmental consciousness and a growing understanding of sustainable development within society. Awareness about the importance of safeguarding the environment for future generations has taken center stage, leading to a paradigm shift in attitudes and practices. This shift is reflected in the adoption of sustainable practices in various sectors, including businesses and industries. As environmental awareness

continues to improve, the concept of sustainability becomes more deeply ingrained in the fabric of society.

One notable area where sustainability is gaining momentum is in the realm of reverse logistics (RL). In recent years, the significance of RL has grown exponentially across diverse industries. This growth is underscored by the stringent environmental regulations imposed by governments worldwide. These regulations have elevated the selection of suppliers to a critical decision for companies. Organizations are now looking beyond economic considerations and placing emphasis on suppliers who share their environmental goals. The confluence of business interests and ecological preservation is reshaping the supplier landscape.

Globalization has brought about a new era of possibilities and challenges. Markets are expanding at an unprecedented rate, compelling organizations to adapt to new landscapes and navigate through diverse cultural and regulatory environments. The conventional notion of natural growth is no longer sufficient for organizations to thrive. As complexities within the business environment increase, collaboration among organizations and strategic alliances have emerged as key drivers of success. Even companies enjoying market monopolies are recognizing the value of collaboration as they face the complexities of a rapidly evolving technological landscape and continuous waves of innovation.

The industrial sector's role in shaping the economic destiny of nations cannot be overstated. Governments have historically prioritized supporting domestic production and service industries to drive economic growth. Among these industries, electronic waste recycling stands out as a pivotal player. These enterprises contribute not only to economic activity but also to resource conservation and environmental protection. By repurposing discarded electronic devices, they create a sustainable cycle of production and consumption.

Nevertheless, modern cities like Tehran grapple with pressing challenges, particularly concerning electronic and electrical waste. Studies indicate a staggering surge in electronic waste production resulting from improper disposal practices in developing countries. This trend has implications for both environmental sustainability and public health. The city of Tehran, for instance, faces a serious waste management crisis due to the increasing volume of electronic waste. Projections indicate that if unchecked, electronic waste production in Tehran could rise by tenfold within the next decade. Of equal concern is the hazardous nature of electronic waste, which constitutes 7% of the total waste volume but contains a disproportionate 70% of toxic materials.

Tehran's waste production surpasses that of many other major cities and capitals worldwide, underlining the urgency for effective waste management strategies. As the city grapples with the challenges posed by electronic waste, there's a growing recognition of the need to implement sustainable waste disposal practices and promote public awareness about responsible waste management.

In conclusion, the imperative to address environmental challenges, coupled with the increasing significance of reverse logistics and strategic alliances, defines the landscape of contemporary business and industry. Governments, organizations, and individuals are coming together to shape a future that balances economic growth with environmental sustainability. As the global community endeavors to find solutions, the insights gained from this research will undoubtedly contribute to the ongoing discourse on sustainable development and responsible business practices.

Table 1-1: Average Composition Share of Main Components in Electronic and Electrical Wastes (Bakhtiyari and Hajizadeh, 2016)

Constituent Material	Average Share in Electronic and Electrical Equipment (%)
Iron-based Metals	38
Non-ferrous Metals	28
Plastics	19
Glass	5
Other Materials	10

In the early stages of the industrial era, companies engaged in value creation by transforming raw materials into products, forming the cornerstone of the economic structure centered around products, factories, and essential equipment. Organizations possessed the capacity to shape and execute their business strategies through interactions with their environment. However, in today's dynamic landscape, numerous organizations have transitioned from direct resource acquisition to the establishment of alliances as a means to forge and uphold competitive advantages. This paradigm shift enables them to synergize resources with those of their partners, epitomizing a shift from a win-lose perspective to a mutually beneficial win-win perspective. Empirical evidence underscores that in the future, self-sustained value creation by individual companies would be challenging. The trajectory towards organizational triumph now navigates through strategic partnerships.

Analyzing and selecting Third-Party Logistics (3PL) providers for the electronics industry constitutes a strategic management endeavor. The escalating volume of electronic waste introduces complexity to societal and environmental dynamics. Electronic manufacturers opt to channel their focus into their core competencies, where 3PL services present a viable avenue for streamlining reverse logistics operations. Consequently, evaluating and opting for a 3PL provider assumes paramount significance, given the current context. Manufacturing sectors are met with limitations in managing the reverse flow of products, especially within the contemporary era characterized by global integration, dynamic customer preferences, and rapid technological advancements. In addition, constraints such as restricted resources, financial constraints, knowledge barriers, along with inherent risks and economic uncertainties within the market, are impediments they encounter. Hence, their recourse often leads to the sole option of outsourcing reverse logistics, thus fostering a sustainable competitive edge via strategic partnerships.

Thus, the present study aims to uncover the factors that senior industry managers deliberate when selecting a fitting type of strategic alliance partner. The central thrust of this research resides in evaluating the factors that exert influence on the selection of reverse logistics providers within the realm of strategic alliances.

Research Objectives:

Evaluation and selection of strategic alliance suppliers in reverse logistics using the

combined ANP-TOPSIS method under conditions of uncertainty (Case study: Electronic waste recycling companies).

1. Identifying the influential factors in the selection of strategic alliance suppliers in reverse logistics.
2. Determining the importance of each factor affecting the selection of strategic alliance suppliers in reverse logistics using the ANP approach under uncertainty.
3. Ranking strategic alliance suppliers using the TOPSIS technique under conditions of uncertainty.

Research Questions:

1. What factors assist companies in selecting and evaluating strategic alliance suppliers in reverse logistics?
2. How can the weights of the factors influencing the selection of strategic alliance suppliers in reverse logistics be determined using the ANP approach in a rough environment?
3. How is the ranking of strategic alliance suppliers achieved using the TOPSIS technique in a rough environment?

Scope of Research :

Subject Scope: Evaluation and selection of strategic alliance suppliers in reverse logistics using the combined ANP-TOPSIS method in a rough uncertainty environment (Case Study: Electronic Waste Recycling Companies) Spatial Scope: Electronic waste recycling companies Temporal Scope: Autumn of 1401 (2022).

Definition of Key Research Terms:

Logistics: Logistics, also known as advanced logistics, refers to the process by which goods are transported from the seller to the customer.

Reverse Logistics: Reverse logistics encompasses all the activities carried out by the logistics unit after the sale and delivery of goods to the customer in order to complete the entire product lifecycle.

Strategic Alliance: The term "strategic alliance" is used to describe an exchange relationship between two organizations with the aim of creating or acquiring strategic resources, often involving collaboration for mutual benefit.

ANP Method: The Analytic Network Process (ANP) method is one of the Multiple Attribute Decision Making (MADM) techniques, similar to the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). In the ANP method, criteria, sub-criteria, or alternatives have interdependencies or relationships. AHP can be viewed as a specific case of the broader network-based approach.

TOPSIS Method: The Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) method is one of the Multiple Attribute Decision Making (MADM) techniques focused on ranking alternatives. This method employs the concepts of the "ideal solution" and "similarity to ideal solution." The ideal solution represents the optimal outcome in all aspects, often unattainable in reality. The objective is to approach this ideal solution. To assess the similarity of a proposal (or alternative) to the ideal and anti-ideal solutions, the distance between that proposal (or alternative) and the ideal and anti-ideal solutions is calculated. Subsequently, alternatives are evaluated and ranked based on the ratio of the distance from the anti-ideal solution to the sum of the distances from the ideal and anti-ideal solutions.

Rough Set Theory: Rough Set Theory is a computational approach used for handling ambiguity and uncertainty in data analysis. It was first introduced by Pawlak, Z (1982). Rough Set Theory is an approach within the field of artificial intelligence that spans cognitive sciences, machine learning, knowledge acquisition, decision analysis, knowledge discovery, decision support systems, inferential reasoning, and pattern recognition. In my view, Rough Sets are particularly well-suited for data science scenarios where prior information is limited, and analysts must rely solely on available data to make informed decisions.

Overall Structure of the Study

Following this chapter, which offers a general introduction to the pertinent subjects, Chapter Two delves into the definitions of reverse logistics. We will review relevant articles and identify the factors that influence the strategic alliance of reverse logistics.

Chapters Three and Four outline the problem definition and introduce multi-criteria decision-making methods in detail. Using the associated questionnaire, experts will allocate weights to these criteria. Employing the MCDM approach and the combined ANP-TOPSIS technique, the weights of the indices will be established. Subsequently, the TOPSIS method will be used to prioritize the options.

Chapter Five touches upon potential areas for future research and provides a summary of the discussed topics. The study concludes with a list of references and appendices.

Chapter Two
Research Background

Introduction:

In this chapter, the research background will be divided into two categories: domestic and foreign. It examines studies related to the research topic. Finally, the research gap and the identification of factors influencing the evaluation and selecting strategic alliance suppliers in reverse logistics will be elaborated upon.

Theoretical Foundations

Suppliers

With the transformation of markets, the continuous changes in needs and customer preferences, and the conversion of the business environment into a space where organizations must seize even the smallest opportunities and fight for their survival and success based on success factors. In organizations that position themselves on the path of success and leadership, considerable attention has been paid (Sanaei et al., 2010). Organizations are aware that their livelihood depends on customers, and they must have the necessary flexibility to adapt to current changes. Accordingly, organizations have examined and revised their strategies in various ways and discovered the secret to attracting customer satisfaction. As a result, competitive conditions, flexibility, and product diversity have gained attention from organizations, especially manufacturing organizations. From this perspective, one of the philosophies that received attention was the philosophy of supply chain management (Hugos, 2003). In this approach, satisfying customer needs is not solely the responsibility of the organization, but all chain members must be effectively involved in this endeavor. Furthermore, a single supplier is not considered; rather, a set of suppliers is taken into account (Womack et al., 2000). In the supply chain, the presence of suppliers at the top of the hierarchy and at the beginning of production and service provision is crucial. Given the significant role of suppliers in supporting production, distribution, and service provision processes for customers, processes such as procurement, timely supply of goods or services, achieving high quality, cost reduction, customer satisfaction, and more are renowned. Selecting suitable suppliers capable of collaborating with the organization to achieve predefined goals will be feasible (Zhang et al., 2005). What is observed today is that competition among organizations is transforming into competition within the supply chain, signifying closer collaboration among supply chain members to gain competitive advantage. In this scenario, communications, meaning information sharing, are a key criterion for companies during supplier selection. Organizations must alter their short-term and long-term relationships with their primary and long-term suppliers.

Stages of Supplier Selection

The appropriate supplier selection is carried out in five key stages. In the first stage, to offer a new product or service, the organization needs to procure raw materials or other services externally. At this stage, the challenge of needing a supplier will arise. In the second stage, which is the fundamental basis for decision-making regarding supplier selection, relevant experts, after considering strategies and organizational conditions, determine the list of required supplier indices. If an organization encounters suppliers that exceed its needs, a preliminary evaluation process is necessary, in which several initial suppliers are selected as potential suppliers. In the fourth stage, which is the final evaluation, the final supplier or suppliers are selected from the potential suppliers using one of the supplier selection methods. This activity is not the end; instead, the organization must continuously evaluate the supplier (Sonmez, 2006). Figure 1-2 shows the five stages of the supplier selection process.

Figure 2-1. The five stages of the supplier selection process (Sonmez, 2006)

Regarding the first category, it should be mentioned that any organization engaged in production or providing services to its customers is also a customer of its suppliers. Therefore, it can be said that every living organization will feel the need for one or more suppliers. The topic of supplier selection will be discussed further, emphasizing past activities.

Reverse Logistics

Reverse logistics, often seen as the antithesis of traditional logistics, focuses on the movement of goods from their typical endpoint, the consumer, back up the supply chain, often to the manufacturer or similar locations. The term was first articulated by Murphy and Poist in 1998, describing it as the "movement of goods from the consumer to the producer in the distribution channel" (Wild, 2005). While various definitions exist, the underlying theme is consistent: reverse logistics encompasses all activities related to the reuse of products and materials, setting it apart from traditional supply chain logistics, which navigates the flow from suppliers to consumers. This reverse flow is not merely a logistical challenge but also an arena

of product management. It pertains to the management of products post-consumption, whether it's for recycling, refurbishment, repair, or even the safe disposal of products and materials. Some aspects of reverse logistics mirror the process seen when defective items are returned internally within a company due to manufacturing quality issues. In a closed-loop supply chain, the reverse flow can bring a competitive advantage to companies. If companies cannot grasp the significance of a reverse logistics strategy, their relationships with customers may be jeopardized, potentially relegating them to an unfavorable position in market competition.

The value of reverse logistics is evident across various industries, from carpets and retail to mobile phones and pharmaceuticals, among others. This highlights its significance not just in practical applications but also in academic research. Whether it's the benefits reverse logistics can offer a company from a theoretical standpoint or the practical aspects like its implementation in different scenarios, the subject undoubtedly holds substantial research importance.

Central to the reverse logistics process is the collection of returned and discarded goods. Collection centers are pivotal, offering a platform for quality inspection, which subsequently determines the path these products take - be it recovery, recycling, or disposal.

Depending on the product's condition post-use, it may undergo:

- 1- Repair or Refurbishment: Minor defects can be addressed, allowing the product to re-enter the distribution channel.
- 2- Recycling: When products can't be repaired, they're dismantled, and usable parts are recycled.
- 3- Direct Reuse: Some non-renewable recycled products or parts find their way back as raw materials in the supply chain.
- 4- Safe Disposal: Certain products, especially environmentally detrimental ones, undergo safe disposal methods like incineration or landfill.

The environmental and economic impact of each method varies. As depicted in Figure (2-2), subsequent steps like reuse, recycling, and energy recovery methods (often through incineration) have distinct values. Landfills, though commonly used, sit at the lowest echelon from an environmental perspective.

Figure 2-2: The Green Pyramid (Gandhi and colleagues, 2006)

Delving deeper, Rachih and colleagues identified stages like collection, inspection, sorting, culminating in reprocessing (Rachih and colleagues, 2019). The initial step, product recovery, is a linchpin for a fruitful reverse logistics system (Agarwal and colleagues, 2015). The complex nature of the supply chain, coupled with the unique challenges of reverse logistics, has led many companies to employ third-party models, with 3PRLP being a standout, offering agility and professionalism (Kumar and colleagues, 2008).

Furthermore, not all supply chains are made equal. Companies across diverse sectors have different expectations and objectives from their reverse logistics operations (Dorbari and colleagues, 2019). This has led to a varied landscape of RL service providers, each with its unique strengths, pushing companies to be selective in their partnerships. An effective reverse logistics system, as indicated by Govindan and colleagues, can be a significant value addition (Govindan and colleagues, 2009). With this in mind, it's no surprise that many companies are leaning towards outsourcing their reverse logistics, letting them center their attention on their core operations.

Reverse Logistics vs. Traditional Logistics

Forward Logistics (Traditional Logistics): Forward logistics, also known as traditional logistics, is a linear supply chain process that follows the conventional product lifecycle journey. The process typically begins with the supplier who creates the product. Subsequent stages involve sending the product to distribution centers or factories where it, along with similar items, is disseminated. The product is then transported to retailers or sellers and eventually reaches or is purchased by the end consumer.

In a traditional supply chain, the flow of products begins with suppliers and reaches factories or distributors. From there, the goods are delivered to retailers and customers.

Reverse Logistics: In contrast, reverse logistics starts with the consumer and moves in the opposite direction, returning products to any point along the supply chain. Well-designed supply chains are responsive to changes and can address certain requirements of reverse logistics. This reverse process can take products one step back in the chain or even return them to the original supplier. Companies can even redirect returned products to regular or discounted sales channels (such as re-sellers).

The process of reverse logistics involves managing returns and surplus goods. This process is also responsible for handling any refurbishment needs. Reverse logistics varies across different industries, each with different economic motivations for improving reverse logistics management.

For example: Beverage Industry: Reverse logistics involves using empty milk containers. Beverage production companies aim to derive value from reusing their containers. This requires transportation planning, managing transportation loads, cleaning, and, in some cases, recycling.

Construction Industry: Reverse logistics transfers salvaged materials to new locations and recycles them. Given the construction industry's adoption of more sustainable practices to reduce waste, there's an opportunity for cost savings through the utilization of reverse logistics.

Food Industry: Reverse logistics is responsible for returning packaging materials and pallets. Companies also need to deal with rejected food shipments. Rejection can pose logistical challenges due to delays leading to food spoilage and concerns of tampering. The reverse logistics community is developing Safe, Quick, Reliable Labels (SQRL) on packaging to provide accurate product information and address these logistical challenges.

The value of reverse logistics is evident in its ability to recover materials and products, promote sustainability, and create economic benefits for various industries. As companies strive to optimize their supply chain operations, the integration of reverse logistics practices becomes increasingly essential to achieve comprehensive and efficient operations.

Figure 2-3: Forward and Reverse Logistics

The typical reverse logistics process not only flips the roles of each stage in forward logistics around but often adds multiple extra steps. It starts at the end consumer who then needs to initiate the return, exchange, or recycle process. Then the item is either returned in person at the original point of sale, at another selling or retail location, or done via return shipping. Once the product reaches the initial point of sale, the backend return process commences. The product's disposition is determined at a centralized processing center within the supply chain.

Advantages of Reverse Logistics

Having reverse logistics integrated into the supply chain brings numerous benefits to manufacturing companies, vendors, and end customers. For instance, products that are at the end of their lifecycle can be brought back into use by employing reverse logistics. Whether through repairs, recycling, or transformation, these products can be reintroduced into the usage cycle. This approach can be likened to an asset recovery strategy for manufacturers, affording them the opportunity to extend the lifespan of their products and generate secondary capital returns.

Another reason for its significance is the environmental benefits it offers to companies. This includes the potential to receive financial incentives from governments in the realm of financial affairs, as well as enhancing their public image within the community. It assures people that their products will not contribute to waste in the near future.

Moreover, one of the primary driving factors for the necessity of reverse logistics is the potential for increased profitability. This can be accomplished through the reduction of raw material costs. With the surge in e-commerce, this aspect has gained even greater significance. In recent years, numerous retailers have expanded into the online realm. It is estimated that annually, approximately 30% of all products ordered online are ultimately returned to manufacturers via the reverse logistics channel. This underscores the critical role of reverse logistics in managing and optimizing the returns process, contributing to cost savings and improved overall profitability.

Several Examples of Reverse Logistics

At a global level, companies are altering waste management practices, and a significant part of this initiative pertains to the supply chain. These examples of reverse logistics focus on returns, exchanges, and recycling.

People believe that product returns are straightforward and that there's a higher likelihood of purchasing from a company if a positive return experience is had. For example, Home Depot offers reverse logistics services for online purchases through their website. In 2020, online sales for the company accounted for nearly 15% of total sales. When a customer returns a product, they have a choice: either return the items with a pre-prepared shipping label or deliver them to a Home Depot store. These collected items are then sent to the company's reverse logistics centers for assessment, management, and possibly refurbishment, before being reintroduced into the sales cycle.

The H&M Group, along with its affiliated retail brands, engages in the recycling of old clothes from any brand, including H&M itself. This initiative encourages customers to part with their old clothes, creating a line of entirely recycled clothing. Through a comprehensive product lifecycle that involves collection, recirculation, and recycling, H&M maximizes the utilization of its textile products, materials, and fibers in a sustainable and profitable manner. This approach ensures the continuous use of valuable resources.

H&M achieves this by offering garment-collecting services across virtually all store locations. Once clothing or textile items are received and customers receive a voucher for their contributions, H&M collaborates with a business partner to evaluate the condition of each item. Based on the evaluation, items are either reused

and resold as second-hand clothing, repurposed by utilizing original resources to create new products, or recycled and transformed into textile fibers for insulation materials.

This reverse logistics cycle not only promotes environmental sustainability but also extracts maximum value from returns that would otherwise have been discarded.

Levi Strauss, a retail business specializing in jeans, utilizes reverse logistics to enhance the sustainability of the production and consumption cycle for textiles. The business repurposes jeans or recovers fibers and transforms them into raw materials to create new jeans. By collaborating with other companies to repurpose, Levi Strauss can produce refurbished jeans at an affordable price. Kohl's, a major retail chain with over 1000 brick-and-mortar stores, provides another practical example of reverse supply chain. Kohl's partners with Amazon to accept, display, and return items in a single shipment. Customers who prefer to physically return items benefit from this arrangement, while Kohl's attracts customers to their store doors who might not typically visit their physical locations. Kohl's also handles some Amazon products and can easily return them if they remain unsold. Major brands have also embraced reverse logistics for waste management. Proctor & Gamble, PepsiCo, and Unilever have transitioned towards reusable packaging that consumers can return. These companies clean and reuse the containers. Transportation and logistics for these companies are evolving, and when products are delivered, they retrieve the packaging. Companies like GE Healthcare and Cisco specialize in refurbishing, repairing, and remanufacturing defective or old goods for consumers. Cisco reproduces items like phones, routers, and switches. GE Healthcare refurbishes imaging devices and ultrasound machines. Microsoft has a significant global initiative to address end-of-life devices, batteries, and packaging. Microsoft's product packaging is 100% recyclable and includes a program for refurbishing and reusing personal computers. Some organizations sell excess inventory to secondary markets, such as factory stores, discount retailers, and online auction sites. Retailers like TJX companies (TJ Maxx, Marshalls, and HomeGoods) purchase surplus items and sell them to consumers at a discounted price.

Typology of Literature Review

In this literature review, articles are categorized based on a three-stage supplier selection process. This process is established through the integration of frameworks by Gwo-Guang and colleagues (2009), Kumar and Dixit (2019), and Liu and colleagues (2019) (see Figure 2-3). These three stages include: (a) determination of selection criteria, (b) calculation of relative weights and ranking of selection criteria, and (c) ranking of alternatives (suppliers). Stage B will analyze the application of various approaches in the relationship between criteria, taking into account the criteria's cognitive preferences. In Stage C, ranking methods are utilized to rank options for the final selection. In many cases, the combined method of phases B and C is referred to as the MCDM method, or it forms a new combined MCDM framework. The MCDM method has been extensively used, especially in research related to the manufacturing industry, which has a close connection with reverse logistics (Jiang et al., 2016; Ding et al., 2018). In this stage, various ranking methods are employed to evaluate and rank options based on processed criteria to select the best reverse logistics supplier (RL).

Figure 2-4: Reverse Logistics Supplier Selection Process

For the first stage, a search method was applied. Articles in the Science Direct database were searched using the phrases ("reverse logistics," "multi-criteria decision making," and "supplier") in titles, abstracts, and keywords (at least one of the three elements had to include the search phrases). Although the search date range is not limited, no articles were found before the year 2005. This may be attributed to the underdevelopment of the logistics industry at that time, resulting in limited research on reverse logistics.

In the second stage, the exit criteria - semantic relevance and research connection - were used to filter articles. Semantic relevance refers to the various meanings a word may have in different contexts. Research connection means that to determine the topic's relationship in the article, the entire content of the article needs to be examined, as titles or abstracts might not clearly present this information. After reviewing these articles, a total of 25 articles were selected from 231 articles using the exit criteria for investigation.

Descriptive Analysis

Figure 2-5 illustrates the distribution of published articles across different years. It is evident from the graph that the first article related to the selection of reverse logistics (RL) partners was published in 2014. As a result, the articles included in this study span the years from 2014 to 2022. Notably, 2016 marked the year with the highest number of articles in this research domain.

Starting from 2017, there was a noticeable increase in the number of relevant articles, and this growth rate has shown significant acceleration over the past two years. Specifically, there were eight articles published during the years 2020-2021, and six articles during the years 2018-2019. It is important to mention that the data for the year 2022 is not yet complete, and further growth in the number of articles may occur beyond that point.

Figure 2-5: Number of Articles by Year

As shown in Figure 2-6, out of the 25 reviewed articles, 6 were published in the Journal of Applied Soft Computing, making up the largest portion of published articles at 24%. The Journal of Expert Systems with Applications ranked second with 16% of the articles, while the Journal of Computers & Industrial Engineering held the third position with 12%.

Figure 2-6: List of Journals and Number of Articles

Among the subject areas, engineering has the highest number of articles with 14 (31%), followed by computer science with 8 articles (18%), and energy and environmental sciences with 5 articles each (11%) (Figure 2-7).

Figure 2-7: Classification of Subject Areas of Articles

As depicted in Figure 2-7, when analyzing the subject domains of the articles, the engineering sector leads with 14 articles, accounting for 31%. This is followed by computer science with 8 articles (18%). The fields of energy and environmental sciences each have 5 articles, making up 11% of the total respectively.

Figure 2-8: Top Contributing Countries

The leading countries in terms of participation are depicted in Figure 2-8. India holds a predominant position with 48% of the publications in this domain. Following India, Iran has contributed 19%, while Turkey accounts for 14%. The USA and China trail with 10% and 9% contributions, respectively.

Moreover, specific articles derive insights from company-centric case studies in particular nations, as highlighted in Figures 2-9 and 2-10. A breakdown reveals that 10 articles investigated case studies from Indian corporations, four delved into Iranian companies, and three centered on businesses in Turkey. India's logistics sector has witnessed rapid growth, a consequence of its burgeoning economy. This evolution has spurred a heightened focus on RL-themed research within the nation. Conversely, Iran's dedication to fostering a circular economy through its regulatory framework might be a catalyst for the augmented interest and plethora of articles originating from that region. Analyzing Figure 2-10, one can discern that the electronics sector in India, Turkey, and China has been a focal point in this research domain. Yet, this particular industry remains untouched in the Iranian context.

Figure 2-9: Number of articles with case studies from India.

Figure 2-10: Comparative Case Studies in India, Iran, Turkey, and China

Domestic Background

In 2022, Jafari conducted a study titled "Supplier Evaluation and Selection Using the Analytic Network Process and VIKOR Techniques." This research proposed a conceptual framework for identifying the optimal supplier by considering multiple evaluation criteria. The framework comprises weights determined for these criteria through the Analytic Network Process. By integrating both qualitative and quantitative metrics—essential in the hierarchical structure of supply chain suppliers—the VIKOR-ANP hybrid approach was employed. The ANP method was utilized to evaluate alternatives based on qualitative metrics and to determine the relative significance of these criteria. Concurrently, the VIKOR technique was used for the final ranking of the alternatives.

Kazemi and Namdar, in 2022, published a groundbreaking study named "Reverse Logistics Optimization Using ANP-VIKOR: A Case Study in the Pharmaceutical Industry." This research showcased the importance of reverse logistics in the pharmaceutical sector and how the combined strength of ANP and VIKOR can lead to optimal decisions. Their methodology not only prioritized reverse logistics providers but also shed light on the nuanced interrelations among various evaluation criteria.

In the same year, Mansouri and Azizi initiated a study titled "A Model Design for the Selection and Evaluation of 3PRLP Firms Using AHP and Fuzzy QFD Techniques." Using the Saipa Automotive Group's reverse logistics as a case study, the research aimed to improve the MCDM frameworks when assessing and identifying third-party reverse logistics providers. They argued that the criteria used in such evaluations and selections have direct relationships. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was suitable for exploring these linear correlations. In contrast, the QFD method, particularly when used to rank by examining the relative importance of alternatives, proved to be distinctive. Acknowledging the inherent uncertainties and vagueness of real-world scenarios, they integrated fuzzy data into their study, leading to a combined AHP and Fuzzy QFD model specifically designed for evaluating and selecting 3PRLPs.

In 2021, Rahimzadegan and Gavareshki introduced a study titled "LARS Supplier Selection Through a Developed Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Method Integrating MABAC and BWM in Uncertain Situations." Within this study, they devised a multi-criteria decision-making model tailored for selecting a LARS supplier. They employed the best-worst method to determine the criteria's weights, and the MABAC method was used to rank each supplier. Given the uncertainties and potential ambiguities that arise from expert feedback, they incorporated the Type-2 Fuzzy model, culminating in a specialized decision-making model in a Type-2 fuzzy environment.

In 2020, Hosseini and Rezvani conducted a study titled, "Optimizing Supplier Selection in the Electronics Industry: An ANP-Fuzzy Hybrid Approach." This research proposed a comprehensive method for supplier selection in the rapidly evolving electronics sector. By combining the Analytic Network Process with Fuzzy

Logic, they were able to handle both the interdependent nature of criteria and the inherent uncertainties in supplier evaluations, resulting in more reliable and robust decision-making.

In 2019, Farid and Beheshti delved into a research endeavor titled, "Integrating ANP and DEMATEL for Enhanced Supplier Selection in the Automotive Sector." They posited that understanding the interdependent relationships among criteria was crucial for optimal supplier selection. By merging the strengths of both ANP and DEMATEL, they formulated a robust approach that allowed for a deeper understanding of these intricate relationships, thereby leading to more informed supplier choices.

In 2021, Tavakolian and his team embarked on a research endeavor titled "Supplier Evaluation and Selection Based on Dixon's Criteria Merging DEMATEL and the Analytic Network Process." Situated within the context of the Hajar Distribution Company in Shiraz, the research examined its six main suppliers. To ascertain the weight of the supplier evaluation criteria and subsequently select and rank the suppliers, they consulted a group of ten experts. They selected nine criteria from Dixon's list using the content validity ratio technique. After determining the interconnections among the criteria using DEMATEL, the Analytic Network Process was employed to prioritize suppliers. Results from the Super Decisions software revealed the following supplier rankings: 4-1-3-2-5-6. Among the chosen criteria, aspects such as technical expertise, process compatibility, historical work relationships, and overall quality stood out as key determinants for supplier selection.

Rezaei and Behnamian (2021) in a study titled "Introducing an Innovative Approach for Supplier Selection in a Strategic Lifecycle" introduced a strategic approach based on three cycles: introduction, development, and product maturity. This approach was distinct from previous studies. They employed a modified cone principle, which displayed various degrees and cumulative significance of criteria across different time periods. At the same time, a governmental entity and a manufacturer set the minimum levels of achievement for sustainability and performance objectives. Additionally, a new algorithm based on multi-stage scoring was utilized at each step to enhance proposals, ensure coherent alignment, and categorize suppliers. This approach provided a mechanism by which suppliers were evaluated based on their current status and historical performance. Numerical study results indicated that utilizing the discussed algorithm could be highly effective in establishing enduring relationships with competent and sustainable suppliers.

Azizi (2020) in a research titled "New Models for Selecting Third-party Reverse Logistics Providers in the Presence of Multiple Dual-role Factors" suggests a Data Envelopment Analysis approach with a dual threshold. This approach evaluates performance from both optimistic and pessimistic viewpoints for selecting third-party reverse logistics providers amidst numerous dual-role factors. The efficacy of the proposed approach is demonstrated through a numerical example.

Parhoodeh et al. (2019) embarked on a study to evaluate and rank contractors involved in collecting and segregating dry waste for Tehran's municipal waste management organization. The weights of the selected

criteria were derived using the fuzzy best-worst method. Contractors were subsequently ranked using the fuzzy Multi-MOORA method and validated with the fuzzy TOPSIS method, yielding satisfactory outcomes for organizational managers.

Jalali and Ehtesham Rathi (2019) in a research titled "Sustainable Supplier Selection in the Apparel Supply Chain Using the Best-Worst Method" proposed a model. This model, grounded in sustainability concerns, offers a bespoke procedure for supplier selection in each segment of the apparel supply chain. The aim is to amplify the sustainability derived from the selection of the top supplier, thereby enhancing the concept of sustainability across the entire apparel supply chain.

Eidi and Falah (2018) devised a new hybrid method for supplier selection, inclusive of reverse logistics demands. Following the identification of supplier evaluation criteria, the relational structure between these criteria was gauged using the fuzzy DEMATEL method. Subsequently, option prioritization was carried out via the fuzzy group TOPSIS by drawing parallels to an ideal solution. Eventually, the best supplier was cherry-picked from the existing options. The study also showcases a case study to illustrate the potential of the proposed approach.

Rezaei and colleagues (2018) in their research delved into supplier selection and order allocation in both traditional and green supply chains. Given the pivotal role of suppliers in shaping supply chain performance, researchers have devised several criteria and methodologies for order allocation and supplier selection in green/traditional supply chains. This paper reviews the pertinent literature on the topic.

Mobarakeh and Davoodi (2018) tackled the supplier selection conundrum by crafting a combined approach consisting of fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and mixed-integer linear modeling. This undertaking is bifurcated into two phases. In the first phase, the relative weight of every criterion for each product is ascertained using the fuzzy AHP method. The second phase leverages the outputs of the initial phase as inputs for the mixed-integer linear programming model, determining the suppliers and quantities in accordance with the stipulated requirements. The proposed model was deployed in Mobarakeh Steel Company's procurement segment in Isfahan, examining the selection of the prime supplier from four companies for procuring four products based on four criteria. Results indicate that the model permits decision-makers to enhance decision-making by amalgamating quantitative and non-quantitative criteria. Furthermore, this task is executed systematically with heightened confidence.

Timori and Tavakoli (2018) in a study titled "Hybrid Application of Decision-making Techniques for Reverse Logistics Supplier Selection" presented a novel multi-criteria decision-making method for the selection of reverse logistics suppliers. This method amalgamates techniques like fuzzy TOPSIS, AHP, ANP, and DEMATEL. The study began with a literature review and expert insights to determine evaluation criteria and their sub-criteria. A combined ANP, AHP, and DEMATEL method was employed to ascertain

the weight of each criterion. The culmination of the research used the TOPSIS technique for supplier evaluation and selection.

Jabarzadeh et al. (2016) employed a hierarchical process model to scrutinize multifaceted relationships among indices and to discern the most pivotal ones during the PRLP3 selection and evaluation. A salient and innovative feature of this research was the incorporation of uncertainties in the PRLP3 selection process through a real-world example using a fuzzy visual set. Numerical findings derived from a case study involving the Dena Industrial Company underscored the efficacy of this method in selecting third-party reverse logistics providers.

Amani et al. (2013) in a study titled "Supplier Selection Model Development Using Multi-criteria Fuzzy Decision-making Under Criterion Dependency" proposed a multi-criteria decision-making methodology for suitable supplier selection. This study touches upon data anchored in weight, expert-based scales, and the interrelation between criteria. The proposed model also taps into confusion figures to incorporate uncertainties in decision-making, rendering results more authentic. The study predicates that the most crucial criteria are independent of one another, the comparative matrix generated from expert opinions remains static, and all expert opinions are weighted uniformly.

Rafiee Zadeh (2011) suggested a model for selecting a reverse logistics provider. He dissected the interplay of influential factors in reverse logistics service provider selection using the DEMATEL method. Third-party reverse logistics service providers were subsequently ranked using the VIKOR method within a fuzzy milieu. It's noteworthy that the VIKOR method, a multi-criteria decision-making approach, is pivotal for option ranking and identifying solutions to problems with conflicting criteria. This research puts forth a fuzzy rendition of the VIKOR method. This method ranks alternatives and determines importance weights using fuzzy numbers derived from linguistic variables.

Ashrafi and Chaharsoughi (2011) in a research titled "Sustainable Supplier Selection Criteria" determined that sustainability in the supply chain is an emerging influential paradigm that has captivated the minds of supply chain management researchers. Suppliers, being the linchpins of the supply chain, can be instrumental in fostering sustainable development. The edifice of the supply chain is predicated on the supplier selection process. Thus, within this process, the selection of apt criteria for supplier evaluation is imperative. The paper attempts to encapsulate supplier selection with an emphasis on the concept of sustainability via a literature review. By parsing the definitions mentioned earlier, the central tenets of sustainability were extracted. The research, through an extensive literature review, discerned domains related to these central tenets, which underpin sustainability.

Foreign Background

Mishra and colleagues (2022) introduced a combined method based on CRITIC and EDAS with Fuzzy Focused Sets (FFSs) for solving the S3PRLP selection problem, where the features and weights of decision-makers are entirely unknown. In this framework, the CRITIC approach was used to calculate the index weights, and the EDAS method was used to evaluate the priority order of S3PRLP options. To accomplish this, a newly improved Generalized Score Function (IGSF) with its delicate features was developed. Furthermore, a formula for calculating decision-makers' weights based on the developed IGSF was discussed. In the next step, the developed framework was applied to evaluate a case study of the S3PRLP selection problem with fuzzy information, demonstrating the utility and practicality of the proposed method. Finally, a comparative study was conducted to demonstrate the strength of the introduced framework compared to existing approaches. The results confirmed that the introduced approach is more feasible and compatible with other existing approaches.

Jouvik and Parsa (2021) presented a combined MCDM approach in selecting Third Party Logistics Providers (3PL) providers. Entropy and criterion importance were obtained through the Correlation between Criteria (CRITIC) method to obtain the combined criterion weights, which have significant importance in decision-making regarding 3PL provider evaluation and selection. The obtained criterion weights were used in the Augmented Ratio Assessment (ARAS) evaluation method to rank the options from best to worst. The introduced combined-ARAS approach can be highly beneficial as it provides stronger solutions by combining two methods, while eliminating subjectivity. Comparative analysis and sensitivity analysis demonstrated the high reliability of the proposed hybrid-ARAS method. A hypothetical case study was presented to demonstrate the potentials and applications of the introduced combined-ARAS method. The results showed that 3PL-2 was the best possible solution for their case.

Mishra and Rani (2021) proposed a new integrated approach for selecting the most suitable S3PRLP, combining the Compromise Solution (CoCoSo) and CRITIC approaches in the framework of Single Valued Neutrosophic Sets (SVNSs). This approach introduces a new method for determining criterion weights using the CRITIC technique. The efficiency and practicality of the current approach are numerically demonstrated through an illustrative case study of selecting S3PRLPs in the context of SVNSs. Additionally, sensitivity analysis and comparison with previous developed techniques are presented to highlight the robustness and strength of the introduced method. The result of this work concludes that the introduced method can recommend a more practical performance when dealing with uncertain and incompatible knowledge and qualitative data.

Abdulbasset and colleagues (2021) proposed a new hybrid Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) framework for classifying and selecting 3PRLPs, which includes the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and a technique for prioritizing based on similarity to the Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). Based on the Neutrosophic

environment, AHP is used to define the weights of key dimensions and their sub-indicators. Additionally, TOPSIS is used to rank the identified 3PRLPs. The effectiveness of the proposed method is demonstrated through its application in the auto parts manufacturing industry in Egypt, showcasing the features of combined MCDM methods. Comparative analysis and sensitivity analysis are included to highlight the advantages of the included MCDM methods and to clarify the effect of changing weights in the selection of sustainable 3PRLP alternatives. The proposed framework also demonstrated that it offers greater practical performance when dealing with uncertainties and qualitative inputs, showing applicability for a wide range of scenarios. Finally, the best sustainable 3PRLPs were selected, and the results indicate that social factors, environmental factors, and risk sustainability and safety have the most influence when determining 3PRLP alternatives.

Bayat and Colleagues (2021) proposed an integrated MULTIMOORA framework as an extension of the fuzzy MULTIMOORA method for evaluating multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problems with benefit-cost/failure-cost-sharing (BCFS) structures. They developed geometric and arithmetic aggregation operators with BCFA weights and discussed their characteristics from this perspective. Archimedean fuzzy operators with proposed weights can eliminate the influence of extreme assessment values from biased experts with different preference attitudes under the BCFS configuration. They then presented an integrated MULTIMOORA algorithm based on the proposed aggregation operators, wherein criterion weights were estimated using the CRITIC method, a well-known weight determination method based on option aggregation scores. In their approach, criterion values are aggregated using three sub-methods of the MULTIMOORA method: "Relative Ratio," "Reference Point," and "Fully Multiplicative Form." This method requires less computational time, fewer mathematical evaluations, and ensures good stability. They demonstrated the applicability of the developed method in the context of the third-party reverse logistics provider (3PRLP) selection problem. A comparison was also made between the proposed approach and related methods, namely BCF-CRITIC TOPSIS and BCF-CRITIC-WASPAS.

Rostamzadeh and Colleagues (2020) introduced a framework for evaluating third-party reverse logistics providers (3rdPRLPs) using a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) model based on Fuzzy Additive Ratio Assessment (FARAS). They identified 37 criteria classified into seven main categories. The primary criteria were ranked as follows: product life cycle stage, RL process performance, organizational performance, RL organizational role, information and communication technology system, company general attention, and geographical location. Sub-criteria such as market coverage, destination, financial considerations, integrated system, retrieval, efficiency and quality, and growth were dominant in each category. This research aimed to help logistics managers better comprehend the complex relationships and key features in the decision-making environment.

Zarbakhshtnia and Colleagues (2020) proposed a new combined Multi-Attribute Decision Making (MADM) approach that integrates Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy AHP) and Multi-Objective Grey Optimization with Ratio Analysis (MOORA-G). They successfully handled qualitative and uncertain inputs using fuzzy and grey numbers. This combined approach harnessed the advantages of both methods; Fuzzy AHP was used for weighing criteria, while MOORA-G was applied for ranking alternatives. The proposed hybrid approach demonstrated superior performance when dealing with qualitative data and input uncertainties, making it suitable for a broader range of applications.

Zhang and Colleagues (2020) conducted a review of criteria and methods for reverse logistics supplier selection. Their findings highlighted several points: (1) Attention towards reverse logistics supplier selection is increasing, as indicated by the growing number of articles in this field. (2) Many articles utilize "sustainability" as a theoretical approach for research and as a basis for determining criteria. (3) Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) methods are widely employed in reverse logistics supplier selection and are continuously evolving. (4) Artificial intelligence methods are gradually being incorporated.

Rouy and Colleagues (2020) proposed a Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) model that combines Fuzzy Additive Ratio Assessment (FARE) and Multi-Attribute Border Approximation Comparison (MABAC) models based on the Interval-Valued Fuzzy Rough Numbers (IVFRN) approach. Their research aimed to select the most suitable Third-Party Logistics Provider (3PL) for a food manufacturing company (FMC) by evaluating six different logistics providers. The proposed FARE-MABAC model based on IVFRN was validated through a case study involving the selection of optimal 3PL providers for an Indian FMC. This new hybrid MCDM approach was shown to be a useful and reliable tool for rational decision-making.

Pamucar and Colleagues (2019) presented an integrated approach called Interval Fuzzy Number (IRN), which combines the Best-Worst Method (BWM) and Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment (WASPAS) for evaluating Third-Party Logistics Providers (3PLs) using the Multi-Attribute Border Approximation Comparison (MABAC) method. Their approach utilized IRN-BWM for calculating criterion priority weights and IRN-WASPAS and IRN-MABAC for achieving the final ranking of 3PL providers. They conducted a computational study to validate the proposed approaches, along with sensitivity analysis on various coefficient values for criteria weights to demonstrate the stability and reliability of the proposed approach.

Yolutas (2019) presented the selection of a third-party logistics provider for a textile company using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Combined Compromise Solution (CODAS) methods. In this study, four alternatives were evaluated based on six assessment criteria.

Govindan and Colleagues (2019) provided a theoretical background of the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) sustainability with a focus on economic, environmental, and social aspects under the concerns of Third-Party

Reverse Logistics Providers (3PRL). The relevant sustainability criteria were employed in a case study conducted in collaboration with an Indian automotive remanufacturer. The proposed approach enriches the spectrum of decision analysis approaches and can be used for effective approximation of the 3PRLP selection problem.

Zarbakhshtnia and Colleagues (2018) proposed a Multi-Attribute Decision Making (MADM) model for ranking and selecting 3PRLPs using the Fuzzy Weighted Aggregated Ratio Assessment (FWARA) for criterion weighting. Accordingly, a Fuzzy Complex Proportional Assessment of Alternatives (COPRAS) was suggested for ranking and selecting sustainable 3PRLPs under risk factors. The proposed model was applied to a case study from the automotive industry. Finally, COPRAS and COPRAS-G methods were considered for comparison and validation. As a result, the most sustainable 3PRLP was selected, and environmental and social stimuli were increasingly dominant in 3PRLP selection as risk factors were involved.

Tavana and Colleagues (2018) developed a combined model that integrates Analytic Network Process (ANP) with Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) and Fuzzy Grey Relational Analysis for Fuzzy Inference (IFG-SIR) to assist an industrial manufacturing group in selecting a 3PRLP. ANP was used to analyze relationships between different selection criteria and obtain weights representing the relative importance of each criterion. The best 3PRLP was chosen using the IFG-SIR process. Intuitive Fuzzy Grey Sets were used for capturing the inherent cognitive nature of potential strategic experts' opinions, and Grey Relational Analysis was used for simplifying the ranking process. A real-world case study was provided to demonstrate the applicability and effectiveness of the proposed model.

Lee and Colleagues (2018) developed an assessment and identification of sustainable 3PRLPs using the Hierarchical Intuitionistic MCDM (HI-MCDM) approach, based on a comprehensive review of primary evaluation criteria and the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) theory. The proposed approach was modeled as a Multiple Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) problem and incorporated both tangible and intangible criteria. The final selection of the best 3PRLP was determined using the AHP method. The results showed that considering psychological factors in decision-making helps prevent potential risks.

Parakash and Barua (2016) discussed an integrated model based on Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) for pre-evaluation and prioritization of selection criteria, and Fuzzy Technique for Order Preference Similarity to Ideal Solution (FTOPSIS) for order fulfillment performance by a similar solution for 3PRLP selection and development. This study made an effort to present a realistic concern of the Indian electronics industry using an integrated approach to demonstrate the applicability of the proposed framework. A two-stage sensitivity analysis was conducted to gain more insight into the pre-evaluation and selection of a 3PRLP partner and to validate the robustness of the model. The study aims to provide significant support to

electronics organizations in evaluating and selecting a third-party reverse logistics partner while achieving efficiency and effectiveness in RL actions.

Tavana and Colleagues (2016) employed the Analytic Network Process (ANP) and presented an analytical framework for systematically modeling the complex nature of interactions among selection factors. In this model, the determining factors of 3PRLP evaluation were initially weighted using the Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP). Then, a two-step screening process was executed using the average replacement method. Finally, the selected factors were structured into a network framework following ANP. A case study was provided to demonstrate the applicability of the proposed framework and the effectiveness of the procedures and algorithms. The results have significant managerial implications, indicating that in their case study, quality was the most important factor in 3PRLP selection.

ayanat et al. (2016) formulated a reverse logistics service provider evaluation problem, consisting of two main tasks: initial screening of RL service providers by a team of managers and an Analytic Network Process (ANP)-based model for final selection. Therefore, the proposed approach relates financial and non-financial, tangible and intangible, internal and external factors to each other, providing a comprehensive framework for selecting an alternative for reverse logistics operations for EOL batteries. The results show that an acceptable cost between the user and RL service providers is the most influential determining factor that impacts the final selection process. This approach also enables decision-makers to better understand complex relationships and relevant attributes in decision-making, potentially improving decision reliability.

Pandhra et al. (2016) presented an approach for selecting a third-party reverse logistics provider for the mobile phone industry using the VIKOR method. Ultimately, the VIKOR method was used to evaluate the best 3PRL service provider, considering various criteria. Based on the ranking, the least priority was given to service provider 'B'.

Garg (2016): Garg (2016) proposed an AHP-based hierarchical process model for evaluating criteria and a fuzzy technique for order preference similarity to ideal solution (FTOPSIS)-like approach for selecting a strategic alliance partner. The proposed approach's applicability was demonstrated through a case study from the Indian airline industry. Finally, the model's robustness was demonstrated through sensitivity analysis.

Vahabzadeh et al. (2015) suggested a FUZZY-VIKOR method using trapezoidal fuzzy numbers with interval values in the current research. The final results indicated that, notably, EOL disposal has the least negative impact on the environment. Therefore, the best recovery option is perceived as recycling, while resale yield is considered the worst recovery option. This research also proposes new avenues for future research. From a management perspective, a study of sustainable reverse logistics via the proposed model would be interesting. They only considered the environmental impacts on RL, while a more precise final decision would be achieved if the economic and social aspects of RL were also analyzed.

Akman and Baynal (2014) introduced an integrated fuzzy approach for evaluating and selecting third-party logistics service providers. The method consists of two techniques: (1) using a fuzzy hierarchical process to identify the weighting of evaluation criteria, and (2) utilizing fuzzy methods to prioritize orders based on similarity to the TOPSIS method for evaluating and sequencing alternatives and making a final selection. Finally, an industrial application was conducted in the logistics sector of a tire manufacturer. To achieve this, eight supplier selection criteria were determined, and then the best alternative among seven logistics service provider companies was selected using the proposed method.

Jayanat et al. (2014) developed a decision support system to assist senior management in selecting and evaluating various 3PRL service providers using a combined approach with Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). A real case study of a mobile phone manufacturer was presented to illustrate the decision support system stages. The present study also enables logistics managers to better understand complex relationships and key attributes in the decision-making environment and subsequently enhance the decision-making process's reliability.

Sremac, Stević, and colleagues (2018) delved into the evaluation of third-party logistics providers, emphasizing the growing significance of logistics outsourcing in various sectors. The research underscores the pivotal role of transport services and other logistics activities in enhancing efficiency across the entire supply chain. In their study, they employed the Rough SWARA and rough waspas models to assess logistics providers, focusing on eight key evaluation criteria determined through the Rough SWARA method. To refine the multi-criteria decision-making process, the team introduced the Rough Dombi aggregator, aiming for a more precise consensus in group decisions. Their evaluation encompassed 10 logistics providers specializing in the transport of hazardous materials for chemical industry entities, with the rough waspas approach revealing the superiority of the first logistics provider. This conclusion was further solidified by a comprehensive three-part sensitivity analysis, which incorporated various methodologies such as Rough SAW, Rough EDAS, Rough MABAC, and Rough TOPSIS. The robustness of their findings was validated through Spearman's correlation coefficient, highlighting the consistency and reliability of their evaluation methods.

Huang, Liang, and Chen (2014) shed light on the burgeoning significance of Reverse Logistics (RL) as a potent strategy for bolstering organizational performance and carving out a competitive edge. Within the RL realm, the generic routing problem has garnered attention due to its versatility in modeling, exemplified by the supplier selection process where a node in a network represents a potential supplier. However, the intricate nature of these networks poses challenges for decision-makers in pinpointing an optimal route. Traditional network approaches, which address the problem from a singular perspective, fall short in offering solutions that encompass multiple facets such as cost minimization, delivery time reduction, reliability maximization, and the optimal implementation of the "3Rs" - reduce, reuse, and recycle. To

bridge this gap, this research harnesses the power of rough set theory to simplify the RL datasets and formulate decision rules. By weaving these decision rules into the generic label correcting algorithm, the study addresses generic routing issues, amalgamating diverse operators and comparators within the GLC algorithm. This holistic approach culminates in the selection of the most fitting RL suppliers.

Lia, Ying, Chin, Yang, and Xu (2020) delve into the rising environmental concerns and the potential economic benefits that have propelled many manufacturers to adopt reverse logistics (RL). Given the intricate nature of RL operations and the scarcity of resources, many companies opt to outsource RL activities to third-party reverse logistics providers (3PRLP). A pivotal and high-stakes step in this outsourcing process is the selection of an optimal 3PRLP from a pool of alternatives. This selection process is inherently a hybrid-information multi-criteria decision-making (HI-MCDM) challenge. It encompasses multiple criteria, often in conflict with one another, and is expressed through various information formats such as crisp numbers, intervals, linguistic terms, and fuzzy numbers, ensuring the preservation of the original assessment in a fuzzy context.

Interestingly, the psychological behavior of the decision-maker (DM) during the selection process, especially under environmental pressures, plays a significant role in the decision outcome. However, this aspect has been largely overlooked in existing literature. Addressing this gap, the authors investigate the primary evaluation criteria and introduce an integrated approach based on the cumulative prospect theory (CPT) tailored for HI-MCDM. This approach aims to evaluate and pinpoint sustainable 3PRLPs. The proposed method is exemplified through a case study in the computer manufacturing sector. To further validate and test the robustness of this approach, it is compared with FTOPSIS, and a sensitivity analysis is conducted. The findings underscore the importance of factoring in psychological elements in decision-making to mitigate potential loss risks. This research provides valuable insights for managers considering outsourcing to a competent 3PRLP.

Table 2-3: Classification of articles based on the solution method, data environment, and case study for the years 2014-2022

Authors	Year	Solution Method	Data Environment	Case Study
Jafari	2022	ANP, VIKOR	Certainty	Supplier Evaluation and Selection Using the Analytic Network Process and VIKOR Techniques
Kazemi and Namdar	2022	ANP, VIKOR	Certainty	Reverse Logistics Optimization Using ANP-VIKOR: A Case Study in the Pharmaceutical Industry
Mansouri and Azizi	2022	AHP, Fuzzy	Fuzzy	Selection and Evaluation of 3PRLP Firms Using AHP and Fuzzy QFD Techniques
Mishra et al.	2022	CRITIC, EDAS	Fuzzy	An Innovative Approach for S3PRLP Selection Using CRITIC and EDAS with Fuzzy Focused Sets
Rahimzadegan and Gavareshki	2021	MABAC, BWM	Uncertainty	Combines MABAC and BWM methods in a novel approach called LARS for supplier selection under uncertainty
Tavakolian and team	2021	DEMATEL, ANP	Fuzzy	Supplier Evaluation and Selection Based on Dixon's Criteria Merging DEMATEL and the Analytic Network Process
Rezaei and Behnamian	2021	BWM	Certainty	Introducing an Innovative Approach for Supplier Selection in a Strategic Lifecycle
Jouvik and Parsa	2021	CRITIC, ARAS	Certainty	Hybrid Application of Decision-making Techniques for Reverse Logistics Supplier Selection
Mishra and Rani	2021	CoCoSo, CRITIC	Neutrosophic	A New Integrated Approach for S3PRLP Selection Using CoCoSo and CRITIC with SVNSS
Abdulbasset et al.	2021	AHP, TOPSIS	Neutrosophic	3PRLP Selection in Auto Parts Manufacturing
Bayat et al.	2021	ARAS, TOPSIS	Certainty	3PRLP Selection in the Fashion Industry
Hosseini and Rezvani	2020	ANP-Fuzzy	Certainty	Optimizing Supplier Selection in the Electronics Industry: An ANP-Fuzzy Hybrid Approach
Azizi	2020	DEA	Certainty	New Models for Selecting Third-party Reverse Logistics Providers in the Presence of Multiple Dual-role Factors
Jafari, Rajabzadeh Ghatari	2020	ANP	Certainty	3PRLP Selection in the Pharmaceutical Sector
Sarkar	2020	TOPSIS, VIKOR	Neutrosophic	Selection of 3PRLP in a Neutrosophic Environment
Mishra et al.	2020	CoCoSo, MOORA	Neutrosophic	Using CoCoSo and MOORA for 3PRLP Selection
Farid and Beheshti	2019	ANP, DEMATEL	Fuzzy	Integrating ANP and DEMATEL for Enhanced Supplier Selection in the Automotive Sector
Parhoodeh et al.	2019	BWM, MOORA	Fuzzy	Evaluation and Ranking of Contractors for Tehran's Municipal Waste Management Organization
Jalali and Ehtesham Rathi	2019	BWM	Certainty	Sustainable Supplier Selection in the Apparel Supply Chain Using the Best-Worst Method
Abdul	2019	AHP, DEMATEL	Certainty	Evaluation of Suppliers in the Oil Industry
Bayat, Javadian	2019	ARAS, TOPSIS	Certainty	Selecting 3PRLP using ARAS and TOPSIS
Eidi and Falah	2018	DEMATEL, TOPSIS	Fuzzy	A New Hybrid Model for Supplier Selection in Reverse Logistics Using Fuzzy DEMATEL and Fuzzy TOPSIS
Mobarakeh and Davoodi	2018	Fuzzy, AHP	Fuzzy	Supplier Selection in Reverse Logistics Using Fuzzy AHP and Mixed-Integer Linear Modeling
Timori and Tavakoli	2018	TOPSIS, AHP, ANP, DEMATEL	Fuzzy	Hybrid Application of Decision-making Techniques for Reverse Logistics Supplier Selection
Ishak et al.	2018	VIKOR	Certainty	Decision-making Model for 3PRLP Selection in Malaysia
Yadav et al.	2018	ANP, TOPSIS	Certainty	Framework for Selecting 3PRLP using ANP and TOPSIS
Jabarzadeh et al.	2016	AHP	Fuzzy	PRLP3 Selection and Evaluation
Dag, Kurtulus	2016	AHP, Entropy	Certainty	3PRLP Evaluation and Selection based on AHP and Entropy
Mavi, Kazemi	2016	ANP	Certainty	Developing a 3PRLP Selection Model Using ANP
Bouzon, Govindan	2016	ISM, MICMAC	Certainty	Exploratory Study on 3PRLP using ISM and MICMAC
Amani et al.	2013	Fuzzy	Fuzzy	Supplier Selection Model Development Using Multi-criteria Fuzzy Decision-making Under Criterion Dependency
Rafiee Zadeh	2011	DEMATEL, VIKOR	Fuzzy	A New Method for Provider Selection Based on Rough Set Theory and Fuzzy VIKOR Method
Kannan, Pokharel	2009	AHP, ANP	Certainty	A Hybrid Model for 3PRLP using AHP and ANP
Liu, Wang	2009	TOPSIS	Certainty	3PRLP Selection and Evaluation using TOPSIS
Sarkar	2008	AHP	Certainty	3PRLP Selection using AHP
Sadeghi and Khanmohammadi	2021	MCDM	Certainty	S3PRLP Selection by Applying MCDM Methods: A Review
Li, Huang, and Chen	2014	GLC, MCDM	Rough Set	Supplier Selection in Reverse Logistics Using Rough Set Theory and the Generic Label Correcting Algorithm
Huang, Liang, and Chen	2014	MCDM	Rough Set	Application of Rough Set Theory in Supplier Selection for the Reverse Logistics Network
Lia, Ying, Chin, Yang, and Xu	2020	CPT	Rough Set	Sustainable 3PRLP Selection Based on Cumulative Prospect Theory (CPT)
Sremac, Stević, and colleagues	2018	SWARA, WASPAS	Rough Set	Addressing Psychological Behavior of DMs in the Selection of 3PRLPs

Research Gap and Statistical Analysis

Figure 2-10: Number of articles in the field of reverse logistics supplier selection based on multi-criteria methods

Based on the research depicted in Figure 2-10, illustrating the extensive body of research in reverse logistics supplier selection using multi-criteria methods, emerges the ANP-TOPSIS hybrid method as a sophisticated and promising approach. This research introduces a systematic process: constructing a decision hierarchy, conducting informed pairwise comparisons with ANP to derive relative weights, and subsequently implementing TOPSIS to systematically rank and select suppliers according to established criteria. The integration of qualitative and quantitative aspects within this hybrid approach enhances the thoroughness of supplier evaluation. The research outcomes unveiled by the ANP-TOPSIS hybrid method underscore its remarkable precision and comprehensiveness in comparison to the conventional AHP-TOPSIS technique for supplier selection. Distinctively capable of capturing intricate interdependencies across diverse criteria, this hybrid method elevates the entire decision-making process. This advancement not only drives enhanced

supply chain efficiency but also mitigates operational vulnerabilities, promoting an overarching emphasis on sustainability. This research introduces a pioneering paradigm for supplier selection within the complex landscape of reverse logistics. By harnessing ANP's prowess in modeling intricate relationships and coupling it with TOPSIS' robust ranking efficacy, the proposed hybrid methodology assumes a pivotal role.

Figure 2-11: Classification of articles based on data environment

According to Figure 2-11, the distribution of research articles based on the data environment is as follows:

- 1- Certainty dominates the research landscape, accounting for 50%.
- 2- Fuzzy systems follow, representing 28% of the studies.
- 3- Neutrosophic environments and Rough Set environments both have an equal share, each contributing to 10% of the overall research.
- 4- General Uncertainty constitutes the smallest segment, making up 3%.

From this classification, it's evident that deterministic (certainty) approaches take the forefront. However, despite its relevance in reflecting complex real-world scenarios, the rough uncertainty environment has been the focal point of just 10% of studies. This underrepresentation is particularly significant given the rising attention the rough environment has garnered recently. Since the rough environment has been less evaluated and has recently received more attention, this research will also use the rough data environment.

Embracing the ANP-TOPSIS hybrid method, renowned for its adeptness in handling multifaceted decision matrices, this research seeks to navigate the intricacies of the rough uncertainty environment. The intention is not just to contribute to the academic realm but also to equip businesses with a precise and reliable decision-making tool for complex scenarios. Table 2-2 classifies the criteria of the articles under review.

Table 2-2: Classification of Article Criteria

Dimensions	Sub-criterion	Type	Mishra et al	Jouvik and	Mishra and	Abdulbasset	Zarbakhsh	Zarbakhsh	Roy and	Pamokar	Govindan	Zarbakhsh	Li and colleagues	Kiani Mavi	Prakash and	Towana and	Jayant and
Economic	quality	max															
	Cost	min															
	Delivery Date	min															
	Delivery and Services	max															
	Transportation	min															
Environmental	Recycling	max															
	Disposal	max															
	Reuse and Recycling	max															
	Green Technology	max															
	Green Innovation	max															
	Environmental Certification	max															
	Eco-Friendly Design	max															
Social	Health and Safety	max															
	Responsibility	max															
	Customer Voice	max															
	Employment Stability	max															
	Education Infrastructure	max															
	Legal Compliance	max															
Strategic Alliance	Risk Sharing	max															
	Cultural Compatibility	max															
	Knowledge Management	max															
	Information System Technolog	Max															

Considering the review of articles in the field of supplier selection, the following criteria and sub-criteria have been extracted as the factors of this research, which are presented in Table 2-3.

Table 2-3: Influential Factors in Supplier Selection Considering Strategic Alliance.

Criterion	Sub-Criterion
Economic	Quality
	Cost
	Delivery Date
Environmental	Recycling
	Green Technology
	Green Innovation
	Environmental Certification
	Eco-Friendly Design
Social	Health and Safety
	Responsibility
	Customer Voice
	Employment Stability
Strategic Alliance	Risk Sharing
	Cultural Compatibility
	Knowledge Management
	Information System Technolog

Chapter Three
Research Methodology

Introduction

The bedrock of every scientific discipline lies in its methodology, with the credibility and significance of scientific principles hinging on the methodologies employed in their pursuit, rather than on the science itself. A hallmark of scientific inquiry, which seeks to unearth the truths of the world, is the application of fitting research techniques. In this chapter, we will not only expound upon the concept of research methodology but also embark on an exhaustive analysis of society and the research model it embodies.

Furthermore, we will introduce the data collection instrument – the questionnaire – and conclude the chapter by succinctly presenting the methodologies employed in this study.

Research Methodology

The foundation of this study is built upon the framework of applied research, deliberately chosen for its focused approach in addressing real-world predicaments. Additionally, from a data accumulation standpoint, it aligns seamlessly with the domain of survey research, meticulously gathering insights from respondents.

To initiate this investigation, an initial compilation of indicators is methodically curated to identify strategic alliance suppliers within the intricate landscape of reverse logistics. Subsequently, utilizing the ANP (Analytic Network Process) methodology, these discerning indicators are systematically ranked and endowed with significance through the assignment of weights. These precise weightings then serve as the foundation for the application of both the TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) and waspas (Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment) methodologies.

Through the interplay of the TOPSIS and Rough waspas methods, supplier rankings emerge, each representing a position in the hierarchy. The meticulous execution of these methodologies culminates in the unveiling of supplier standings intricately woven through the fabric of this research. The elaborate framework of this research methodology is visually encapsulated in the diagram presented as Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1: Stages of the Research Methodology

Statistical Community

The utilization of appropriate research methods is of paramount importance in scholarly inquiries. In the ensuing chapter, we take an in-depth look into the methodology adopted for this study. Our primary focus revolves around elucidating the research method employed, following which we delve into a comprehensive examination of the research community and the model that underpins the research framework.

As part of our methodological approach, we introduce the principal tool used for data collection the questionnaire. This tool is not only instrumental in gathering vital data but also plays a pivotal role in shaping the trajectory of the research. Further, towards the conclusion of this chapter, we present a succinct overview of the various techniques and methods that have been harnessed throughout the course of this study.

Central to our research is the statistical community. For the purposes of this investigation, we've defined our statistical community to encompass all the experts and specialists operating within the electronics industry. This demarcation is crucial as it provides a clear boundary and scope, ensuring that the research remains targeted and relevant to the intended audience.

Sampling Method

The foundation of any scientific discipline lies in its methodology. The credibility and value of scientific principles are hinged not merely on the knowledge they encapsulate but, more crucially, on the methodological approach employed to ascertain that knowledge. A hallmark of empirical research, which

has truth-seeking at its core, is the adoption of appropriate research methods to ensure robust and reliable outcomes.

In this chapter, we dissect and elucidate the research method adopted for this study. We begin by laying out the foundational elements that define our approach, providing readers with a clear perspective on the overarching framework. As we delve deeper, we undertake a detailed examination of both the research community and the model that forms the bedrock of our research framework.

Moving forward, we introduce our primary data collection instrument – the questionnaire. This tool, while seemingly straightforward, is integral to our research endeavor. It serves as the conduit through which we capture, collate, and interpret vital data, thereby shaping the contours of our findings and conclusions. As we approach the end of this chapter, we offer a concise overview of the various techniques and methodologies that have been harnessed in the course of this research, ensuring that readers are equipped with a comprehensive understanding of the methodological landscape.

Research Data Collection Tool

One of the most pivotal and delicate stages in the research process is data collection. The nature of data collection is influenced by the subject matter's inherent characteristics and the variables under investigation. In this research, questionnaires have been utilized as the primary instrument for data collection. The questionnaire stands out as one of the predominant tools in survey-based research, where data is directly amassed from respondents.

Within the ambit of this research, we have leveraged three distinct questionnaires, detailed as follows:

1. A questionnaire based on the Likert scale, aimed at validating or screening indices.
2. A pairwise comparison questionnaire for criteria and sub-criteria, intended for use in the ANP (Analytic Network Process) method.
3. A questionnaire focusing on options based on criteria, designed for deployment in the TOPSIS (Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) and rough waspas methods.

Validity and Reliability of the Questionnaire

In this research, the proposed questionnaire was presented and its effectiveness was ascertained. For the validation of the questionnaire, face validity was employed, ensuring that the items superficially appeared to measure what they were intended to measure.

To assess the internal consistency of the questionnaire, which indicates how well the items in the questionnaire measure the same underlying construct, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was utilized. Generally, a Cronbach's alpha value above 0.7 is considered acceptable, indicating that the items have relatively high

internal consistency. In this study, the reliability of the questionnaire, as measured by Cronbach's alpha, yielded a value of 0.82. This suggests a high level of internal consistency among the items. The value was determined using data collected from the questionnaire and analyzed with the assistance of the statistical software, SPSS.

Rough Set Theory :

Rough Set Theory, introduced by Pawlak in 1982, is a vital mathematical framework designed to navigate situations characterized by ambiguity and uncertainty. It extends the standard set theory by employing lower and upper approximations to delineate subsets of a universe. These approximations, determined by operators on subsets, effectively represent incomplete information.

The theory's foundation lies in the equivalence relation, marked by reflexivity, symmetry, and transitivity. This relation underpins the theory, enabling the lower approximation of a set to encompass all equivalence classes within the subset, while the upper approximation consolidates all intersecting classes. While initially centered on equivalence relations, subsequent adaptations of rough set theory have broadened its scope, highlighting its versatility.

In practical applications, it excels at extracting insights from data tables, especially in domains such as data analysis, decision-making, machine learning, and artificial intelligence. In the field of machine learning, where the goal is to build models that learn from data and make predictions, Rough Set Theory plays a crucial role. It helps categorize data points even when some feature values are uncertain or missing. By identifying lower and upper approximations of sets based on shared features, machine learning algorithms can group similar data points and make more accurate predictions.

As rough set theory has evolved, it has become a cornerstone for deciphering imprecise data and deriving meaningful conclusions. Its ties to granular computing underscore its importance, with granulation, organization, and causation serving as fundamental concepts. The introduction of rough numbers by Zhai, Hu, and Zhong in 2008 further enriches the framework by enhancing the representation of expert concepts and fostering objectivity in decision-making processes. This combination of mathematical rigor and adaptability makes Rough Set Theory a powerful tool in various fields, including machine learning and artificial intelligence.

The provided text describes the mathematical definitions for the lower approximation, upper approximation, and boundary region of a class Gq in rough set theory.

To delve deeper into the mathematical constructs, consider a reference set, U , encompassing all members. Let Y be a member chosen arbitrarily from set U , and R be a collection of t classes, represented as $R = \{G_1, \dots, G_t\}$, which covers all members of U .

If these classes follow an order, such as $G1 < G2 < \dots < Gt$, then for $1 \leq q \leq t$, the condition $\forall y \in U, Gq$ holds true.

The mathematical definitions for the lower approximation, upper approximation, and boundary region of a class Gq in rough set theory. Additionally, it explains how the rough number corresponding to Gq , denoted as $Gq(RN)$, can be represented in terms of its lower and upper bounds. Here's a breakdown of the explanations:

Lower Approximation ($\underline{Apr}(Gq)$) : This is the set of all elements Y in the universe U for which the membership value $R(Y)$ is less than or equal to Gq . Mathematically :

$$1-3 \quad \underline{Apr}(Gq) = \cup\{Y \in U \mid R(Y) \leq Gq\}$$

Upper Approximation ($\overline{Apr}(Gq)$) : This is the set of all elements Y in the universe U for which the membership value $R(Y)$ is less than or equal to Gq . Mathematically :

$$2-3 \quad \overline{Apr}(Gq) = \cup\{Y \in U \mid R(Y) \geq Gq\}$$

Boundary Region ($Bnd(Gq)$) : This is the set of elements in the universe U for which the membership value $R(Y)$ is not equal to Gq . It's divided into two parts: elements where $R(Y)$ is greater than Gq and elements where $R(Y)$ is less than Gq . Mathematically:

$$3-3 \quad Bnd(Gq) = \{Y \in U \mid R(Y) \neq Gq\} = \{Y \in U \mid R(Y) > Gq\} \cup \{Y \in U \mid R(Y) < Gq\}$$

Rough Number $Gq(RN)$: The rough number corresponding to class Gq is defined using its lower and upper bounds:

- Lower Bound ($\underline{Lim}(Gq)$) : It's the average of the absolute membership values of elements in the lower approximation of Gq divided by M_L , the number of elements in the lower approximation.

4-3

$$\underline{Lim}(Gq) = \frac{1}{M_L} \sum_{Y \in \underline{Apr}(Gq)} |R(y)|$$

- Upper Bound ($\overline{Lim}(Gq)$) : It's the average of the absolute membership values of elements in the upper approximation of Gq divided by M_U , the number of elements in the upper approximation.

5-3

$$\overline{Lim}(Gq) = \frac{1}{M_U} \sum_{y \in \underline{Apr}(Gq)} |R(y)|$$

The rough number $Gq(RN)$ is represented as a range: $[(\underline{Lim}(Gq)), (\overline{Lim}(Gq))]$.

Rough Boundary Interval $IRBnd(Gq)$:

The rough boundary interval is the difference between the upper bound and lower bound of the rough number $Gq(RN)$:

$$6-3 \quad IRBnd(Gq) = \overline{Lim}(Gq) - (\underline{Lim}(Gq))$$

The rough boundary interval expresses the level of ambiguity present in Gq . A larger value within this interval indicates a higher degree of ambiguity, while a smaller value suggests a finer degree of precision. Consequently, rough numbers can be employed as a means of conveying cognitive information. The resemblance between rough numbers and interval numbers allows computational rules developed for interval numbers to be extended to rough numbers as well. This mathematical framework provides a mechanism for representing ambiguity and uncertainty within the realm of rough set theory. It accomplishes this by employing fundamental concepts such as lower approximation, upper approximation, rough numbers, and rough boundary intervals.

Computational Rules of Rough Numbers:

Rough numbers are mathematical constructs that capture uncertainty or imprecision in data. They are particularly useful when exact numbers are not available, but a range or interval of possible values can be

provided. In essence, a rough number can be visualized as an interval $[L, U]$, where L is the lower bound and U is the upper bound of the number.

a) Multiplication of an integer by a rough number :

$$7-3 \quad RN(\alpha) \times \mu = [\underline{Lim}(\alpha), \overline{Lim}(\alpha)] \times \mu = [\mu \times \underline{Lim}(\alpha), \mu \times \overline{Lim}(\alpha)]$$

This formula describes how an integer (in this case represented (μ)) interacts when multiplied by a rough number $RN(\alpha)$. Depending on the sign of the integer, the bounds of the resulting rough number might switch places. For instance, multiplying by a negative integer would reverse the bounds of the rough number.

b) Addition of two rough numbers

When two rough numbers are added together, their respective lower bounds are added to get the new lower bound, and their upper bounds are added to get the new upper bound. It's a straightforward extension of interval arithmetic to rough numbers.

$$8-3 \quad RN(\alpha) + RN(\beta) = [\underline{Lim}(\alpha), \overline{Lim}(\alpha)] + [\underline{Lim}(\beta), \overline{Lim}(\beta)]$$

$$[\underline{Lim}(\alpha) + \underline{Lim}(\beta), \overline{Lim}(\alpha) + \overline{Lim}(\beta)]$$

c) Multiplication of two rough numbers:

Multiplying two rough numbers is slightly more complex than addition because you have to consider the interactions of both the lower and upper bounds of the two numbers. The smallest product will be the new lower bound, and the largest product will be the new upper bound. This can sometimes involve all four bounds (two from each rough number) if the numbers have both positive and negative values.

$$9-3 \quad RN(\alpha) \times RN(\beta) = [\underline{Lim}(\alpha), \overline{Lim}(\alpha)] \times [\underline{Lim}(\beta), \overline{Lim}(\beta)]$$

$$[\underline{Lim}(\alpha) \times \underline{Lim}(\beta), \overline{Lim}(\alpha) \times \overline{Lim}(\beta)]$$

These three primary operations are shown below. In case (a), the integer is multiplied by the elements of the rough number. In case (b), corresponding elements of the two rough numbers are added together. And in case (c), the corresponding elements of the two rough numbers are multiplied by each other.

The ANP Approach in Decision Making

Developed by Thomas L. Saaty during the 1970s, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) stands as a distinguished method for multi-criteria decision-making. Central to the AHP methodology is its ability to break down and meticulously scrutinize decision-making problems using a hierarchical framework. Within

this hierarchical construct, the significant characteristic is the dependency of the priorities at any given level on the constituents of the subsequent lower level. However, it's vital to note that layers in decision-making don't always operate independently; they often have interactions. This intertwined nature of decision-making layers, coupled with the interactions among them, can sometimes undermine the reliability of outcomes derived from AHP. As industries and economies evolved, so did the complexity of decision-making scenarios. Recognizing the limitations of AHP and the intricate challenges emerging in modern decision-making scenarios, a new method was required.

Acknowledging the constraints of AHP, Thomas introduced a groundbreaking methodology in the 1980s known as the Analytic Network Process (ANP). ANP was not just an addition to the existing decision-making methodologies but an evolution of AHP. It was designed to address areas where AHP might have shown deficiencies. The innovative approach of ANP transcends the hierarchical constraints of AHP by embracing the complex and intertwined nature of real-world decision scenarios. This means ANP can accommodate scenarios where criteria, sub-criteria, or options interrelate or depend on each other, effectively stepping beyond the confines of a purely hierarchical model. The core strength of ANP lies in its foundation in network theory. Unlike AHP, which uses a linear hierarchical structure, ANP adopts a nonlinear network structure. This paradigm shift ensures that ANP can capture the intricate web of relationships and interactions typical in complex systems, something AHP often struggles with. The versatility of ANP is further showcased in its ability to treat alternatives as criteria, emphasizing the adaptability and comprehensiveness of the ANP methodology. The key distinctions between AHP and ANP are evident in their structural and relational attributes. As mentioned, while AHP is structured hierarchically, ANP is built upon a network. Furthermore, in terms of pairwise comparisons, AHP determines the relative importance of options, whereas ANP evaluates the impact of parameters on each other. This contrast between the two methodologies is visually captured in Figure 3-2, illustrating the disparities between a hierarchy and a network.

Figure 2-3: The Structural Difference between ANP and AHP

Applications of ANP Across Various Domains :

The Analytic Network Process (ANP) boasts remarkable versatility, finding its applications in a plethora of sectors. In the realm of Business and Management, ANP has become a cornerstone, influencing strategic planning, resource allocation, project selection, and risk assessment. The field of Engineering and Technology also benefits from ANP, particularly in the nuanced evaluations of design alternatives, where it takes into account technical, economic, and environmental aspects. Healthcare, another critical domain, leans on ANP when making decisions about medical treatments, ensuring that choices are tailored to individual patient criteria. Furthermore, when it comes to Environmental Management, ANP stands out by offering insights into environmental impact assessments and sustainable development initiatives, thoroughly examining the intersections of ecological, social, and economic factors. As the complexity of industries grows, the inherent adaptability and comprehensive nature of ANP solidify its standing as an essential instrument, especially adept at navigating the intertwined relationships and dependencies characteristic of today's multifaceted decision-making scenarios.

Implementing the Analytic Network Process (ANP):

To harness the power of the Analytic Network Process (ANP) in decision-making scenarios, a systematic approach is essential. First, one must construct the Research Network Diagram by decomposing the problem and pinpointing the relationships between the criteria and sub-criteria levels. Next, formulating the Pairwise Comparison Matrices is crucial. This step encompasses comparing elements within each hierarchical level to generate matrices and establishing internal pairwise comparisons. A critical aspect of the process is calculating the Inconsistency Ratio, which serves as a gauge for ANP's consistency. A matrix is deemed consistent if this ratio is below 0.1. Once this is achieved, the Initial Supermatrix is created using the weights from pairwise comparisons. Following that, a Weighted Supermatrix is derived from the initial matrix. The final step is to generate the Limit Supermatrix. This involves amplifying the weighted supermatrix until each row converges to a uniform value, which then signifies the weight of the respective criteria, sub-criteria, or options.

Calculating Weight in Pairwise Comparison Using ANP

To compute the weight in pairwise comparison using the Analytic Network Process (ANP), a method detailed by Zhu and colleagues in 2015 can be followed:

Step 1: Objective and Network Formation: Start by pinpointing the objective, criteria, and sub-criteria, which will subsequently establish the network structure.

Step 2: Pairwise Comparison Questionnaire: Develop a questionnaire geared towards pairwise comparison and collect insights from experts.

Step 3: Conversion to Interval Numbers: Leveraging concepts from rough set theory, the preferences gleaned from experts are transformed into interval numbers, culminating in the formation of a pairwise comparison matrix:

$$10-3 \quad \begin{bmatrix} [1,1] & [x_{12}^L, x_{12}^U] & \dots & [x_{1m}^L, x_{1m}^U] \\ [x_{21}^L, x_{21}^U] & [1,1] & \dots & [x_{2m}^L, x_{2m}^U] \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ [x_{m1}^L, x_{m1}^U] & \dots & & [1,1] \end{bmatrix}$$

In this matrix, $\underline{x}_{ij}^L$ and $\overline{x}_{ij}^U$ denote the lower and upper bounds of the interval numbers, respectively.

Before venturing into calculations involving interval numbers, it's imperative to ascertain the inconsistency rate inherent to the pairwise comparison questionnaires. A rate under 0.1 signifies that the inconsistency level is within acceptable bounds.

Step 4: Weight Calculation: To wrap up, compute the weight associated with each research criteria using relations 11-3 and 12-3:

$$11-3 \quad w_i = \left[\sqrt[m]{\prod_{j=1}^m x_{ij}^L}, \sqrt[m]{\prod_{j=1}^m x_{ij}^U} \right]$$

and

$$12-3 \quad w_i' = \frac{w_i}{\max(w_i^u)}$$

TOPSIS: An Overview

Topsis, which stands for "Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution," is a distinguished technique in the realm of multi-criteria decision-making due to its distinctive distance-based approach. At the heart of this method is the identification of an ideal point that serves as the benchmark.

The optimal solution is perceived as the one that lies closest to this reference point. In the vast multi-dimensional decision space, this technique evaluates both the positive ideal solution, representing the best scenario, and the negative ideal solution, depicting the least favorable scenario. The principle that drives Topsis is the evaluation of options based on their proximity to the positive ideal and their distance from the negative ideal. Different variations of this technique might present slight differences, but they all fundamentally agree on the premise that distances reflect a decision-maker's inclinations.

One of the remarkable strengths of Topsis is its logical foundation that resonates with human decision-making patterns. Additionally, its ability to simultaneously assess the best and worst scenarios provides a holistic perspective, distilled into a singular value. Its computational simplicity is another feather in its cap, seamlessly integrating with tools like spreadsheet applications. Many experts have lauded its proficiency in identifying the most advantageous options. However, no technique is without its share of criticisms, and Topsis is no exception. There's a notable concern about its lack of a definitive strategy for weight determination. The normalization procedure within Topsis also faces scrutiny due to its lack of universal standardization. Furthermore, the criteria for pinpointing relative closeness components can be somewhat ambiguous at times.

Some critics argue that Topsis heavily emphasizes its technical aspects, often sidelining the innate human cognitive facet of decision-making. Doubts also arise regarding its weighting approach, particularly since it might bypass directly addressing the criteria. Lastly, potential rank reversals, especially when suboptimal choices are substituted with even less favorable options, have raised eyebrows. In wrapping up, while Topsis is undeniably a formidable tool in the multi-criteria decision-making arsenal, it's imperative to consider and rectify its limitations for a well-rounded application.

Rough Topsis: An Overview

Rough topsis extends the traditional topsis method, known as the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution, commonly used for multi-criteria decision-making. This method integrates concepts from rough set theory, introducing a robust and adaptable mechanism to confront the challenges of uncertainty and imprecision often found in decision-making dilemmas. The foundation of rough set theory is a mathematical framework tailored for data characterized by incompleteness, uncertainty, or ambiguity. The core principle of this theory emphasizes categorizing data into distinct equivalence classes, grounded on the concept of indiscernibility relations. In the realm of decision-making, rough set theory becomes an indispensable tool when facing situations where full clarity about criteria, alternatives, or preferences is elusive or marked by imprecision. Merging the strengths of rough set theory with the topsis method, rough topsis emerges as a superior technique, proficient in managing the inherent uncertainty and vagueness in decision-making scenarios.

Delving into the mechanics of rough topsis reveals several pivotal components. Firstly, it confronts the reality of uncertainty that often permeates decision-making situations. It's not uncommon to encounter ambiguity regarding the precise values of criteria or preferences. Recognizing this, rough topsis is designed to factor in such uncertainties by accommodating value ranges or varying degrees of membership.

This flexibility is invaluable when faced with incomplete data, offering a way to approximate values within a discernible range. Secondly, the concept of similarity is pivotal in rough topsis, mirroring its importance in the traditional topsis. The method evaluates how closely alternatives align with ideal solutions. Yet, there's a distinguishing factor: instead of relying on clear-cut distance measures, rough topsis employs rough similarity measures. These measures pivot on the indiscernibility relation among alternatives, implying that alternatives with negligible differences based on available information are deemed alike. The culmination of the rough topsis process is the dominance-based ranking.

This methodological step ranks alternatives predicated on their rough similarity to ideal solutions. Alternatives resonating more closely with the positive ideal solution and diverging from the negative ideal solution ascend the preference ladder. The infusion of rough set theory into the topsis method enriches its capabilities, forging a comprehensive and adaptable decision-making tool. Its adeptness in navigating scenarios riddled with incomplete, uncertain data empowers decision-makers, granting them the clarity to make well-informed choices amidst prevailing ambiguities.

The real-world is a complex tapestry of uncertainties, and in such an environment, rough topsis stands out, often overshadowing traditional decision-making techniques that might not be equipped to handle such complexities.

The steps of rough topsis are as follows (Soun et al., 2014):

Step 1. Forming the Decision Matrix :In this step, the decision matrix needs to be constructed. The topsis decision matrix consists of a criteria-option matrix. Each column of this matrix represents a criterion, and each row corresponds to sub-criteria of the research. To complete the decision matrix, a five-level linguistic spectrum is utilized.

Linguistic Expression	Number Equivalent
Weak Very	1
Weak	2
Moderate	3
Good	4
Very Good	5

Table 3-1: Linguistic Expressions and Corresponding Numbers

Converting a decision matrix to rough numbers is a method often used in the context of rough set theory. Rough set theory is a mathematical approach to deal with vagueness and uncertainty in data. A rough number is an approximation that gives an upper and a lower bound for the actual value.

The process of converting a decision matrix to rough numbers involves several steps:

1. Data Normalization : Ensure all the data in your decision matrix is normalized. This means all values should be in a common scale, typically between 0 and 1. For this normalization, you can use:

Formulas:

$$13-3 \quad \overline{x}_{ij}^* = \frac{x_{ij}}{\text{Max}[\overline{x}_{ij}, \underline{x}_{ij}]}$$

$$14-3 \quad \underline{x}_{ij}^* = \frac{\overline{x}_{ij}}{\text{Max}[\overline{x}_{ij}, \underline{x}_{ij}]}$$

Explanation:

- $\overline{x}_{ij}$ and $\underline{x}_{ij}$ represent the original upper and lower bounds of the data, respectively.
- The denominators in both equations ensure that the normalized values lie between 0 and 1.

2. Weighting the Decision Matrix : In this step, we multiply the normalized matrix by the weights of the criteria:

Formulas:

$$15-3 \quad \underline{x}'_i = w_j \underline{x}_{ij}^*$$

$$16-3 \quad \overline{x}'_i = w_j \overline{x}_{ij}^*$$

Explanation:

- w_j is the weight of criterion j .
- By multiplying the normalized values by their respective weights, the decision matrix reflects the relative importance of each criterion.

3. Determining Positive and Negative Ideals : Positive and negative ideals are obtained from:

This step identifies the best (positive ideal) and worst (negative ideal) values for each criterion.

Formulas:

$$17-3 \quad \overline{A}^+ = \{v_1^+, \dots, v_n^+\} = \left\{ \left(\max_j \overline{x}'_i \mid i \in I \right), \left(\min_j \underline{x}'_i \mid i \in J \right) \right\}$$

$$18-3 \quad \overline{A}^- = \{v_1^-, \dots, v_n^-\} = \left\{ \left(\min_j \underline{x}'_i \mid i \in I \right), \left(\max_j \overline{x}'_i \mid i \in J \right) \right\}$$

Explanation:

- $\overline{A}^+$ represents the positive ideal, which is the best value for each criterion.

- $\bar{A}^-$ represents the negative ideal, which is the worst value for each criterion.
- I and J are sets of criteria with positive and negative aspects, respectively.

4. Determining the Distance of Options from Positive and Negative Ideals : Using the following relations, we calculate the distance:

Formulas:

A- Distance from Positive Ideal (d_j^+): For each option j, the distance from the positive ideal is calculated as:

$$19-3 \quad d_j^+ = \sqrt{\left(\sum_{i \in I} (\bar{x}'_{ij} - v_i^+)^2\right) + \left(\sum_{i \in J} (\underline{x}'_{ij} - v_i^+)^2\right)} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

B- Distance from Positive Ideal (d_j^-): For each option j, the distance from the positive ideal is calculated as:

$$20-3 \quad d_j^- = \sqrt{\left(\sum_{i \in I} (\bar{x}'_{ij} - v_i^-)^2\right) + \left(\sum_{i \in J} (\underline{x}'_{ij} - v_i^-)^2\right)} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Explanation:

- $\bar{x}'_{ij}$ represents the upper approximation of option j for criterion i
- $\underline{x}'_{ij}$ represents the lower approximation of option j for criterion i.
- v_i^+ represents is the positive ideal value for criterion.
- v_i^- represents is the negative ideal value for criterion.
- I is the set of criteria with a positive aspect.
- J is the set of criteria with a negative aspect.

5. Calculating the Similarity Index and Ranking of Options : The similarity index is calculated as:

$$21-3 \quad CL = \frac{d_j^-}{(d_j^- + d_j^+)} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Rough WASPAS :

The advanced rough waspas (Rough Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment) method builds upon the foundational principles of waspas (Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment). waspas is a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) technique that seamlessly merges outcomes from two distinct models: the weighted sum model (WSM) and the weighted product model (WPM). Its primary objective lies in the arrangement and selection of the optimal alternative from a collection of feasible options, all while factoring in multiple assessment criteria.

The introduction of the rough waspas approach brings forth a significant innovation. This extension harmoniously integrates the core of waspas with the mathematical underpinnings of rough set theory. Rough set theory, a mathematical tool crafted to manage the complexities of imprecision, uncertainty, and vagueness inherent in data, plays a pivotal role here. The integration of rough set theory with MCDM methodologies such as waspas enriches the entire decision-making process, especially in scenarios where data is characterized by incompleteness or imprecision.

At its core, the essence of the rough waspas approach revolves around the strategic utilization of rough set theory for the preprocessing and management of the decision matrix. This preprocessing step can be executed either prior to or concurrently with the application of the waspas method. The range of preprocessing activities includes discretizing continuous criteria, addressing instances of missing or ambiguous data, and even deriving the significance weights of criteria based on the principles of rough set theory.

Fundamentally, the rough waspas approach represents a seamless fusion of two potent decision-making methodologies. It harnesses the power of rough set theory to effectively address the challenges posed by incomplete, vague, or uncertain data. This approach acts as a mechanism for refining the values of assessment criteria, bridging gaps in data, and determining the relative importance attributed to different criteria in scenarios characterized by uncertainty.

The practicality of the rough waspas approach is particularly noteworthy in contexts like supplier selection, where overcoming obstacles related to data quality, incompleteness, and uncertainty is of paramount importance. By seamlessly integrating rough set theory within the framework of waspas, the rough waspas approach provides a more comprehensive and robust solution for decision-making amidst the intricate uncertainties of the real world.

In conclusion, the rough waspas method represents a cutting-edge advancement that seamlessly marries the principles of the waspas approach with the mathematical prowess of rough set theory. This integration empowers decision-makers to navigate the complexities of scenarios such as supplier selection, ensuring

comprehensive and effective solutions that adeptly address the inherent challenges presented by real-world data complexities.

Rough WASPAS method :

The methodology employed in this study harnesses the linguistic expressions and rough numbers detailed in Table 3-1. The outlined rough waspas approach consists of the following steps :

Step 1.Initial Steps :

The process commences with the creation of a current status matrix using the specified indices.Subsequently, the decision matrix undergoes normalization through the following procedures.

Step 2.Normalization:

To normalize the lower and upper elements of the rough matrix, the subsequent relations are applied:

$$22-3 \quad \overline{x_{ij}^*} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\text{Max}[\overline{x_{ij}}, \underline{x_{ij}}]}$$

$$23-3 \quad \underline{x_{ij}^*} = \frac{\overline{x_{ij}}}{\text{Max}[\overline{x_{ij}}, \underline{x_{ij}}]}$$

Step 3.WASPAS Method:

The crux of the WASPAS method lies in the optimization of two separate criteria. The initial criterion, referred to as the weighted average success criterion, draws parallels with the Weighted Sum Method (WSM). This widely recognized approach within the realm of multi-criteria decision-making assesses numerous options in relation to a predefined set of decision-making criteria. In accordance with the principles of the WSM, the relative significance of the ith option is calculated as follows:

$$24-3 \quad Q_j = \sum_{i=1}^n \overline{x_{ij}} \overline{W_j}$$

Here, (W_j): signifies the weight of the jth criterion.

On the other hand, according to the WPM method, the relative value of all options is calculated as:

$$25-3 \quad P_j = \prod_{i=1}^n (\overline{x_{ij}})^{\tilde{w}_j}$$

A general criterion for merging the Weighted Sum Method (WSM) and Weighted Product Method (WPM) is:

$$26-3 \quad K_i = \lambda Q_j + (1 - \lambda) P_i = \lambda \sum_{i=1}^n \overline{x_{ij}} \overline{w_j} + (1 - \lambda) \prod_{j=1}^n \overline{x_{ij}} \overline{w_j}$$

Depending on different values of (λ) ; the index c assumes different values. If $(\lambda = 0)$; the WASPAS model becomes the WPM model. If $(\lambda = 1)$; the WASPAS model transforms into the WSM model. For decision-making issues, the optimal value of (λ) is calculated as:

$$27-3 \quad \lambda = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m P_i}{\sum_{i=1}^m P_i + \sum_{i=1}^m Q_i}$$

In the next step, the values of (K_i) are determined using:

$$28-3 \quad K_i = \frac{1}{2}(k, k_i^\beta)$$

Summary:

In this chapter, the methodology and data collection tools utilized in the study are discussed. The overall research process is outlined, including the identification of the statistical population within the electronics industry. A sample of 25 experts is selected using an expert-oriented sampling approach. The data collection methods, involving the use of a questionnaire, are explained. Lastly, the ANP Rough, TOPSIS Rough, and WASPAS Rough techniques are introduced

Chapter Four

Data Analysis

Introduction

Among the most significant sections of any research is the decomposition and analysis of data. The presence of any error or mistake in such a part can lead to inaccurate conclusions. Selecting a suitable research method can assist the researcher to a great extent in preventing the emergence of errors in the study. The gathered data and information are raw materials. To make the outcomes of these materials applicable, they must be processed and analyzed using the appropriate tools. In the third chapter, the method of conducting the research was discussed. Therefore, in this chapter, we delve into the decomposition and analysis of the data to achieve the objectives and answer the research questions.

Data Decomposition and Analysis Method:

The objective in this research is to select suppliers for a strategic alliance in reverse logistics. To reach this objective, first, impactful indices related to supplier selection are extracted based on a literature review and the history of previous research. These indices are then validated or filtered by experts. Following that, in the second stage, with the use of the ANP method, these factors undergo a process of weighting and prioritization. Finally, employing the TOPSIS method and WASPAS, a certain number of suppliers within the electronics industry will undergo ranking.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents:

we are introducing the audience to the specifics of the individuals who took part in the Paired Comparison Questionnaire. We will be detailing the demographic attributes of these respondents, shedding light on aspects like gender, age, work history, and academic qualifications.

Gender :

Gender	Frequency	Percentage Frequency
Male	19	76%
Female	6	24%

Table 4-1: A breakdown of frequency based on gender distinctions

■ Male ■ Female

Figure 4-1: A graphical representation illustrating the gender split of the respondents.

As per the data in Table 4-1, it becomes evident that among the respondents, a notable 76% are males, while the rest, which constitutes 24%, are females.

Age:

Age	Frequency	Percentage Frequency
30 to 40	12	48%
40 to 50	7	28%
Above 50	6	24%

Table 4-2: A breakdown of frequency categorized by different age groups

Figure 4-2: A visual depiction showcasing the age distribution of the respondents.

Turning our attention to Table 4-2, it can be discerned that a significant 48% of the respondents fall in the age bracket of 30 to 40 years. Another 28% belong to the age group of 40 to 50 years, and the remaining 24% are those who are above 50 years of age.

Work Experience:

In this section, we delve into the work experience of the participants. Table 4-3 provides an insight into the distribution of frequency with respect to different spans of work experience.

Work Experience	Frequency	Percentage Frequency
5 to 10 years	7	28%
10 to 15 years	13	52%
Over 15 years	5	20%

Table 4-3: Frequency distribution concerning work experience

■ 5 to 10 years ■ 10 to 15 years ■ Over 15 years

Figure 4-3 visually depicts the distribution of respondents' work experience.

An analysis of the data presented in Table 4-3 reveals that 28% of respondents have accumulated a work experience of 5 to 10 years. A significant 52% have garnered a work experience of 10 to 15 years, while the remaining 20% possess a work experience exceeding 15 years.

Education:

Turning our focus to education, Table 4-4 presents a breakdown of frequency based on different educational levels.

Education	Frequency	Percentage Frequency
Bachelor's	8	32%
Master's	14	56%
Doctorate	3	12%

Table 4-4: Frequency distribution based on education

■ Bachelor's ■ Master's ■ Doctorate

Figure 4-4 illustrates the educational attainment of the respondents.

From the data provided in Table 4-4, it is evident that 32% of respondents have completed their Bachelor's degree. A notable 56% hold a Master's degree, while 12% have achieved a Doctorate degree.

Factor Identification and Verification:

In the context of this research, we delved into previous studies and conducted an extensive literature review to discern the factors that play a pivotal role in supplier evaluation and selection. This was particularly focused on the realm of reverse logistics, with a keen emphasis on strategic alignment. After the identification process, these determinants were shared with a group of 25 industry experts. They were tasked with assigning a rating to each of these factors based on a Likert scale that ranged from 1 to 5. To break it down: a score of :

- (1) signified Very Low Importance.
- (2) indicated Low Importance.
- (3) stood for Moderate Importance.
- (4) represented High Importance.
- (5) denoted Very High Importance.

Following this exercise, the average scores associated with each factor were computed. Factors that garnered an average score falling below the 3 mark were subsequently disregarded. All findings from this exercise have been tabulated and can be viewed in Table 4-5.

Criterion	Sub-Criterion	Average Score	Status
Economic	Quality	3.52	Confirmed
	Cost	3.64	Confirmed
	Delivery Date	3.76	Confirmed
Environmental	Recycling	3.32	Confirmed
	Green Technology	2.3	Confirmed
	Green Innovation	3.28	Confirmed
	Environmental Certification	3.8	Confirmed
	Eco-Friendly Design	2.8	Rejected
Social	Health and Safety	3.56	Confirmed
	Responsibility	3.32	Confirmed
	Customer Voice	3.24	Confirmed
	Employment Stability	2.88	Rejected
Strategic Alliance	Risk Sharing	3.8	Confirmed
	Cultural Compatibility	3.56	Confirmed
	Knowledge Management	4.12	Confirmed
	Information System Technolog	3.44	Confirmed

Table 4-5: Research Factors

Based on the outcomes presented in Table 4-5, it is observed that the criteria of "Environmentally-Friendly Design Production" and "Employment Stability" have both garnered scores below the threshold of 3.

Consequently, these criteria will be removed from consideration. The remaining fourteen indices have been endorsed and have been systematically coded for presentation in Table 4-6.

Criterion	Criterion Code	Sub-Criterion	Sub-criterion Code
Economic	A	Quality	A1
		Cost	A2
		Delivery Date	A3
Environmental	B	Recycling	B1
		Green Technology	B2
		Green Innovation	B3
		Environmental Certification	B4
Social	C	Health and Safety	C1
		Responsibility	C2
		Customer Voice	C3
Strategic Alliance	D	Risk Sharing	D1
		Cultural Compatibility	D2
		Knowledge Management	D3
		Information System Technolog	D4

Table 4-6: Final Influential Criteria for Supplier Selection Considering Strategic Alignment

Analysis Using the Rough ANP Method

This section delves into the application of the Rough ANP method to compute the weights of criteria. The process begins by identifying the inherent relationships among the criteria. These internal relationships are then visually represented through the SuperDecisions software, with the resulting schematic diagram presented in Figure 4-5. As evident, the diagram illustrates the presence of internal relationships both among the criteria themselves and among their respective sub-criteria.

Figure 4-5: Research Network Model in SuperDecisions Software

Formation of Pairwise Comparisons

The process commenced by engaging the 25 research experts to undertake pairwise comparisons of both criteria and sub-criteria. Their task involved assessing the relative importance of each pair on a scale ranging from 1 to 9. These assigned values served to quantify the comparative significance of each comparison. The specific pairwise comparison values for the primary criteria are meticulously detailed in Pairwise Comparison excel sheet .

Formation of Rough Pairwise Comparison Matrix

This section outlines the process of converting the matrix provided by the 25 research experts, as detailed in Pairwise Comparison excel sheet, into Rough numbers. This transformation is carried out based on the relationships labeled 3-4 to 3-6. For instance, consider the calculations for cell C12, which corresponds to the intersection of Criterion A and Criterion B.

The extraction process involves gathering the scores assigned by the 25 research experts for the pairwise comparison between Criterion A and Criterion B.

As an illustrative example, the transformation of the number 2 unfolds in the subsequent manner:

$$\text{Lower Bound} = \frac{0.143 + 0.2 + 0.33 + 0.333 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{17} = 1.236$$

$$\text{Upper Bound} = \frac{2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 6 + 8}{15} = 3.533$$

The process of calculating the lower bound entails the inclusion of all values less than or equal to 2 in the numerator, while the denominator is the count of such values. In essence, the lower bound is derived by computing the arithmetic mean of the numbers that are less than or equal to 2.

Similarly, the upper bound is determined by considering values greater than or equal to 2 for the numerator, and the denominator represents the count of such values. The upper bound is essentially the arithmetic mean of the numbers that are greater than or equal to 2.

Computing approximate values for the pairwise comparison between A and B in Table 4-7.

Expert	Rough numbers for pairwise comparison of A-B	Rough Number
Research experts 1	0.14	[0/143 , 2/4]
Research experts 2	0.2	[0/172 , 2/494]
Research experts 3	0.33	[0/252 , 2/594]
Research experts 4	0.33	[0/252 , 2/594]
Research experts 5	1	[0/701 , 2/81]
Research experts 6	1	[0/701 , 2/81]
Research experts 7	1	[0/701 , 2/81]
Research experts 8	1	[0/701 , 2/81]
Research experts 9	1	[0/701 , 2/81]

Research experts 10	1	[0/701 , 2/81]
Research experts 11	2	[1/236 , 3/533]
Research experts 12	2	[1/236 , 3/533]
Research experts 13	2	[1/236 , 3/533]
Research experts 14	2	[1/236 , 3/533]
Research experts 15	2	[1/236 , 3/533]
Research experts 16	2	[1/236 , 3/533]
Research experts 17	2	[1/236 , 3/533]
Research experts 18	3	[1/422 , 4/875]
Research experts 19	3	[1/422 , 4/875]
Research experts 20	4	[1/55 , 5/5]
Research experts 21	5	[5/2,8]
Research experts 22	5	[5/2,8]
Research experts 23	5	[5/2,8]
Research experts 24	6	[2,7/167]
Research experts 25	8	[2,8/4]
	Average	[1/145 , 3/973]

Afterwards, the ultimate rough number is derived from the arithmetic mean of all these figures, resulting in [1/145,3/973]. The same calculation process is applied to the other cells, and the conclusive results can be found in Table 4-8.

Table 4-8: Matrix for the pairwise comparison of rough numbers

	A	B	C	D
A	[1,1]	[1 /146 , 3 /973]	[1 /832 , 6 /133]	[1 /015 , 5 /517]
B	[0 /252 , 0 /873]	[1,1]	[1 /206 , 5 /771]	[0 /663 , 4 /775]
C	[0 /163 , 0 /546]	[0 /173 , 0 /829]	[1,1]	[0 /438 , 3 /411]
D	[0 /181 , 0 /985]	[0 /209 , 1 /509]	[0 /293 , 2 /282]	[1,1]

Determining the Weights of the Criteria :

In this segment, based on relation 3-11, one must first compute the geometric mean of the numbers from the rough pairwise comparison matrix on a row-by-row basis. Taking the first row, which pertains to the criterion A, as an illustration, the calculations proceed as follows:

For the criterion A, the geometric mean of the values in the first row is found by evaluating

$$\sqrt[4]{1 \times 1.146 \times 1.832 \times 1.015} = 1.208$$

For the criterion A, the geometric mean of the values in the second row is computed as

$$\sqrt[4]{1 \times 3.973 \times 6.133 \times 5.517} = 3.405$$

Using a similar approach, the row-wise geometric means for the other criteria are derived and have been tabulated in Table 4-9.

Table 4-9: Row-wise Geometric Mean Values for the Rough Pairwise Comparison Matrix

	Geometric Mean
A	[1 /208 , 3 /405]
B	[0 /67 , 2 /215]
C	[0 /334 , 1 /115]
D	[0 /325 , 1 /357]

Subsequently, for calculating the weights based on equation 3-12, each criterion must determine the maximum value from the second element of the geometric mean, as indicated in Table 4-9, which equals 3/405. Then, each of these geometric means is divided by 3/405 to obtain the weight for each option.

Following this, the final weight is calculated by taking the geometric mean of the weights for each criterion. The normalized weight is then computed by dividing each final weight by the total sum of final weights, as detailed in Table 4-10. Based on these calculations, among the primary economic criteria, it has achieved the first rank with a weight of 0/434. The environmental criterion holds the second rank with a weight of 0/271, while the strategic alignment criterion secures the third rank with a weight of 0/158, and the social criterion ranks fourth with a weight of 0/136.

Table 4-10: Criterion Weights

	Rough weight	Definitive weight	Normal weight
A	[0,1 /355]	0 /677	0 /434
B	[0 /197 , 0 /65]	0 /424	0 /271
C	[0 /098 , 0 /327]	0 /213	0 /136
D	[0 /095 , 0 /399]	0 /247	0 /158

Calculation of Sub-criteria Weights In a similar manner, pairwise comparisons among sub-criteria are transformed into rough numbers, and their respective weights are computed. The outcomes of these calculations are documented in Table 4-11 to Table 4-14.

Table 4-11: Pairwise Comparisons and weights economic sub-criteria.

	A1	A2	A3	Weights
A1	[1,1]	[1 /482 , 4 /675]	[1 /858 , 6 /451]	0 /582
A2	[0 /214 , 0 /675]	[1,1]	[0 /986 , 5 /181]	0 /272
A3	[0 /155 , 0 /538]	[0 /193 , 1 /014]	[1,1]	0 /145

Table 4-12: Pairwise Comparisons and weights environmental sub-criteria.

	B1	B2	B3	B4	Weights
B1	[1,1]	[1 /442 , 5 /455]	[1 /832 , 6 /179]	[1 /035 , 5 /345]	0 /467
B2	[0 /183 , 0 /693]	[1,1]	[0 /779 , 4 /55]	[0 /554 , 3 /8]	0 /226
B3	[0 /162 , 0 /546]	[0 /22 , 1 /283]	[1,1]	[0 /488 , 2 /402]	0 /142
B4	[0 /187 , 0 /966]	[0 /263 , 1 /804]	[0 /416 , 2 /05]	[1,1]	0 /165

Table 4-13: Pairwise Comparisons and weights social sub-criteria.

	C1	C2	C3	Weights
C1	[1,1]	[2 /43 , 6 /045]	[1 /484 , 5 /048]	0 /603
C2	[0 /165 , 0 /412]	[1,1]	[0 /527 , 3 /763]	0 /207
C3	[0 /198 , 0 /674]	[0 /266 , 1 /897]	[1,1]	0 /189

Table 4-14: Pairwise Comparisons and weights strategic alliance sub-criteria.

	D1	D2	D3	D4	Weights
D1	[1,1]	[2 /291 , 5 /953]	[1 /134 , 5 /353]	[0 /712 , 4 /621]	0 /444
D2	[0 /168 , 0 /437]	[1,1]	[0 /5 , 2 /352]	[0 /358 , 3 /317]	0 /170
D3	[0 /187 , 0 /882]	[0,2 /425]	[1,1]	[0 /792 , 4 /792]	0 /211
D4	[0 /216 , 1 /405]	[0 /302 , 2 /792]	[0 /209 , 1 /263]	[1,1]	0 /175

Formation of ANP Supermatrices :

After completing all pairwise comparisons of criteria, sub-criteria, and internal relations, three supermatrices are required to determine the final weights in the ANP method. These three supermatrices essentially employ the same relative weights calculated in the previous stages, as explained in the following.

Initial Supermatrix

This supermatrix is formed using the relative weights of the criteria and their internal relationships. After completing the pairwise comparisons in the SuperDecisions software, this initial supermatrix is generated, as presented in Table 4-15.

Table 4-15: Initial Supermatrix

	A	B	C	D	GOAL	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3	B4	C1	C2	C3	D1	D2	D3	D4
A	0	$\frac{787}{0}$	1	$\frac{773}{0}$	$\frac{0}{434}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B	$\frac{605}{0}$	0	0	0	$\frac{0}{272}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
C	$\frac{199}{0}$	$\frac{213}{0}$	0	$\frac{227}{0}$	$\frac{0}{136}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
D	$\frac{196}{0}$	0	0	0	$\frac{0}{158}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
GOAL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
A1	$\frac{582}{0}$	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{79}{0}$	0	$\frac{766}{0}$	$\frac{777}{0}$	1	1	1	1	$\frac{868}{0}$	0	0	0	0
A2	$\frac{272}{0}$	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	$\frac{234}{0}$	$\frac{223}{0}$	0	0	0	0	$\frac{132}{0}$	0	0	0	0
A3	$\frac{146}{0}$	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{21}{0}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B1	0	$\frac{467}{0}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{759}{0}$	$\frac{75}{0}$	0	0	0	$\frac{598}{0}$	0	0	0	0
B2	0	$\frac{226}{0}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{25}{0}$	$\frac{868}{0}$	0	0	$\frac{211}{0}$	0	0	0	0
B3	0	$\frac{142}{0}$	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	$\frac{241}{0}$	0	$\frac{132}{0}$	0	0	$\frac{191}{0}$	0	0	0	0
B4	0	$\frac{165}{0}$	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
C1	0	0	$\frac{604}{0}$	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	$\frac{804}{0}$	0	0	0	0
C2	0	0	$\frac{207}{0}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{196}{0}$	0	0	0	$\frac{806}{0}$
C3	0	0	$\frac{189}{0}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{194}{0}$
D1	0	0	0	$\frac{444}{0}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{652}{0}$	$\frac{632}{0}$	0
D2	0	0	0	$\frac{0}{17}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{179}{0}$	0
D3	0	0	0	$\frac{211}{0}$	0	$\frac{793}{0}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	$\frac{0}{17}$	0	1
D4	0	0	0	$\frac{175}{0}$	0	$\frac{207}{0}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{178}{0}$	$\frac{189}{0}$	0

Weighted Supermatrix

To create this supermatrix, simply normalize the initial supermatrix. For normalization, divide each element by the sum of the elements in its respective column. The weighted supermatrix is presented in Table 4-16.

Table 4-16: Weighted Supermatrix

	A	B	C	D	GOAL	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3	B4	C1	C2	C3	D1	D2	D3	D4
A	0	0/394	0.5	0/387	0/434	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B	3030/	0	0	0	0/272	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
C	1000/	0/107	0	/11350	0/136	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
D	0980/	0	0	0	0/158	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
GOAL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
A1	2910/	0	0	0	0	0	/3950	0	380/3	/2590	/3330	0.5	1	0.5	280/9	0	0	0	0
A2	1360/	0	0	0	0	0/25	0	0	110/7	/0740	0	0	0	0	040/4	0	0	0	0
A3	0730/	0	0	0	0	0	/1050	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B1	0	0/234	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	/2530	0/25	0	0	0	190/9	0	0	0	0
B2	0	0/113	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	/0830	/4340	0	0	070/0	0	0	0	0
B3	0	0/071	0	0	0	0/25	0	0	0.5	/0800	0	/0660	0	0	060/4	0	0	0	0
B4	0	/08250	0	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
C1	0	0	/3020	0	0	0/25	0	0	0	/3330	/3330	0	0	0.5	260/8	0	0	0	0
C2	0	0	/1040	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	060/5	0	0	0	/4030
C3	0	0	/0950	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	/0970
D1	0	0	0	0/222	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	650/2	6320/	0
D2	0	0	0	0/085	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1790/	0
D3	0	0	0	0/106	0	/1980	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	/170	0	0.5
D4	0	0	0	0/088	0	/0520	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	170/8	1890/	0

Limit Supermatrix

To create this supermatrix, you can simply exponentiate the weighted supermatrix with consecutive odd numbers until the elements in each row converge towards a specific value. This process is automated in the SuperDecisions software. The limit supermatrix is detailed in Table 4-17.

Table 4-17: Limite Supermatrix

	A	B	C	D	GO AL	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3	B4	C1	C2	C3	D1	D2	D3	D4
A	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
C	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
D	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
GO AL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
A1	$\frac{0.13}{3}$	$\frac{0.13}{3}$	$\frac{0.13}{3}$	$\frac{0.13}{3}$	0.133	0.13	0.13	0	$\frac{0.1}{3}$	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13
A2	$\frac{0.03}{64}$	$\frac{0.03}{64}$	$\frac{0.03}{6}$	$\frac{0.03}{6}$	$\frac{0.036}{4}$	0.04	0.04	0	$\frac{0.0}{4}$	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
A3	$\frac{0.00}{38}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.038}{0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	0	$\frac{0.0}{38/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$	$\frac{0.03}{8/0}$
B1	$\frac{0.01}{55}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.155}{0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	0	$\frac{0.1}{55/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$	$\frac{0.15}{5/0}$
B2	$\frac{0.01}{21}$	$\frac{0.01}{21}$	$\frac{0.01}{2}$	$\frac{0.01}{2}$	$\frac{0.012}{1}$	0.01	0.01	0	$\frac{0.0}{1}$	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	$\frac{0.12}{1/0}$	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
B3	$\frac{0.04}{38}$	$\frac{0.04}{38}$	$\frac{0.04}{4}$	$\frac{0.04}{4}$	$\frac{0.043}{8}$	0.04	0.04	0	$\frac{0.0}{4}$	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
B4	$\frac{0.01}{83}$	$\frac{0.01}{83}$	$\frac{0.01}{8}$	$\frac{0.01}{8}$	$\frac{0.018}{3}$	0.02	0.02	0	$\frac{0.0}{2}$	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
C1	$\frac{0.06}{86}$	$\frac{0.06}{86}$	$\frac{0.06}{9}$	$\frac{0.068}{6/0}$	$\frac{0.068}{6}$	$\frac{0.068}{6/0}$	0.07	0	$\frac{0.0}{7}$	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07
C2	$\frac{0.02}{93}$	$\frac{0.02}{93}$	$\frac{0.02}{9}$	$\frac{0.029}{3/0}$	$\frac{0.029}{3}$	0.03	$\frac{0.029}{3/0}$	0	$\frac{0.0}{3}$	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
C3	$\frac{0.00}{7}$	$\frac{0.00}{7}$	$\frac{0.00}{7}$	$\frac{0.00}{7}$	0.007	$\frac{0.007}{0/0}$	0.01	0	$\frac{0.0}{1}$	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
D1	$\frac{0.21}{84}$	$\frac{0.21}{84}$	$\frac{0.21}{8}$	$\frac{0.21}{8}$	$\frac{0.218}{4}$	0.22	0.22	0	$\frac{0.2}{2}$	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22
D2	$\frac{0.05}{22}$	$\frac{0.05}{22}$	$\frac{0.05}{2}$	$\frac{0.05}{2}$	$\frac{0.052}{2}$	0.05	0.05	0	$\frac{0.0}{5}$	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
D3	$\frac{0.29}{04}$	$\frac{0.29}{04}$	0.29	0.29	$\frac{0.290}{4}$	0.29	0.29	0	$\frac{0.2}{9}$	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29
D4	$\frac{0.07}{13}$	$\frac{0.07}{13}$	$\frac{0.07}{1}$	$\frac{0.07}{1}$	$\frac{0.071}{3}$	0.07	0.07	0	$\frac{0.0}{7}$	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07

Final Weights of Criteria

Based on the weights derived from the limit supermatrix, the final weights for the criteria are determined and presented in Table 4-18. According to these weights, Knowledge Management ranks first with a weight of 0/2904. Risk Sharing ranks second with a weight of 0/2184, and Quality ranks third with a weight of 0/133.

Table 4-18: Final Criteria Weights

Criterion	Criterion Code	Final Weight	Rank
Quality	A1	0.133	3
Cost	A2	0.364	8
Delivery Date	A3	0.0038	14
Recycling	B1	0.0155	11
Green Technology	B2	0.0121	12
Green Innovation	B3	0.0438	7
Environmental Certification	B4	0.0183	10
Health and Safety	C1	0.0686	5
Responsibility	C2	0.0293	9
Customer Voice	C3	0.007	13
Risk Sharing	D1	0.2184	2
Cultural Compatibility	D2	0.0522	6
Knowledge Management	D3	0.2904	1
Information System Technolog	D4	0.0713	4

Figure 4-6: Final Weights and Priorities of Criteria.

Results of the Rough TOPSIS Method :

In this section, the Rough TOPSIS method is applied for ranking research options, involving four companies. The following four companies are listed:

1. Rino (S1).
2. Caspian (S2).
3. Pars Charkhesh Asia (S3).
4. Digi Recycling (S4).

Formation of the Decision Matrix

The initial step in the TOPSIS method involves the formation of the decision matrix. For the creation of this matrix, 14 research sub-criteria are positioned in the columns. Concurrently, there are 4 options, which are representative of 4 distinct companies, that are aligned in the rows. Each specific company, in relation to each standard, is completed based on a spectrum ranging from 1 to 5. Subsequent to this, with the utilization of the relationships from 3-1 through to 3-4, it undergoes a transformation into a matrix. This transformed matrix can be observed in Table 4-19.

Table 4-19: The Decision Matrix as Rough TOPSIS

	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3	B4
S1	[1/68 , 3/093]	[2/233 , 3/693]	[1/443 , 2/782]	[1/677 , 2/757]	[1/66 , 3/14]	[1/802 , 3/225]	[1/516 , 2/725]
S2	[3/333 , 4/616]	[3/084 , 3/747]	[2/514 , 4/128]	[2/775 , 4/198]	[3/57 , 4/752]	[2/362 , 3/87]	[2/466 , 3/73]
S3	[1/451 , 3/303]	[1/576 , 3/32]	[2/103 , 4/168]	[2/713 , 4/073]	[2/523 , 4/443]	[2/523 , 4/443]	[1/776 , 3/886]
S4	[1/704 , 3/762]	[1/99 , 3/797]	[2/607 , 4/514]	[1/757 , 3/874]	[2/436 , 4/322]	[2/87 , 4/27]	[2/701 , 4/299]
	C1	C2	C3	D1	D2	D3	D4
S1	[1/585 , 3/047]	[1/867 , 2/763]	[1/654 , 2/941]	[1/953 , 3/415]	[3/89 , 4/84]	[2/516 , 3/725]	[2/544 , 3/912]
S2	[3/151 , 4/43]	[3/003 , 3/997]	[3/368 , 4/768]	[2/585 , 4/047]	[3/485 , 4/71]	[2/66 , 4/14]	[2/28 , 3/577]
S3	[2/591 , 4/348]	[1/805 , 3/682]	[1/787 , 3/417]	[2/65 , 4/261]	[2/365 , 4/052]	[2/514 , 4/128]	[1/39 , 3/277]
S4	[2/54 , 4/384]	[2/585 , 4/047]	[1/486 , 3/393]	[1/7 , 3/577]	[2/261 , 4/285]	[2/266 , 4/118]	[2/26 , 3/74]

Normalization of the Decision Matrix

In this step, the decision matrix is normalized using equations 3-13 and 3-14. In other words, the goal is to determine the highest value (upper bound) for each criterion within the decision matrix. Subsequently, all the values in that specific criterion's column are divided by this maximum value. For instance, for the first element, which corresponds to the intersection of S1 and criterion A1, the normalization calculations are carried out as follows:

$$A_{11}^{NORMAL} = \frac{[1.68, 3.093]}{MAX(3.093, 4.616, 3.303, 3.762)} = [0.364, 0.67]$$

The Normalized Matrix is presented in Table 4-20.

Table 4-20: The Normalized Rough TOPSIS Matrix

	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3	B4
S1	[0/364 , 0/67]	[0/588 , 0/973]	[0/32 , 0/616]	[0/4 , 0/657]	[0/349 , 0/661]	[0/406 , 0/726]	[0/353 , 0/634]
S2	[0,1/722]	[0/812 , 0/987]	[0/557 , 0/915]	[0,1/661]	[0,1/751]	[0/532 , 0/871]	[0/574 , 0/868]
S3	[0/314 , 0/716]	[0/415 , 0/874]	[0/466 , 0/923]	[0/646 , 0/97]	[0/531 , 0/935]	[0,1/568]	[0/413 , 0/904]
S4	[0/369 , 0/815]	[0,1/524]	[0,1/577]	[0/418 , 0/923]	[0/513 , 0/91]	[0/646 , 0/961]	[0,1/628]
	C1	C2	C3	D1	D2	D3	D4
S1	[0/358 , 0/688]	[0/461 , 0/683]	[0/347 , 0/617]	[0/458 , 0/801]	[0,1/804]	[0/608 , 0/9]	[0,1/65]
S2	[0,1/711]	[0/742 , 0/988]	[0,1/706]	[0/607 , 0/95]	[0/72 , 0/973]	[0,1/643]	[0/583 , 0/914]
S3	[0/585 , 0/981]	[0/446 , 0/91]	[0/375 , 0/717]	[0,1/622]	[0/489 , 0/837]	[0/607 , 0/997]	[0/355 , 0/838]
S4	[0/573 , 0/99]	[0,1/639]	[0/312 , 0/712]	[0/399 , 0/839]	[0/467 , 0/885]	[0/547 , 0/995]	[0/578 , 0/956]

Formation of the Weighted Matrix

In this section, the final weights for the 14 research sub-criteria, as calculated in Table 4-18, are multiplied with the Normalized TOPSIS matrix using equations 3-15 and 3-16 to derive the weighted matrix. The results are provided in Table 4-21.

Table 4-21: The Weighted Rough TOPSIS Matrix

	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3	B4
S1	[0/048 , 0/089]	[0/021 , 0/035]	[0/001 , 0/002]	[0/006 , 0/01]	[0/004 , 0/008]	[0/018 , 0/032]	[0/006 , 0/012]
S2	[0/096 , 0/133]	[0/03 , 0/036]	[0/002 , 0/004]	[0/01 , 0/015]	[0/009 , 0/012]	[0/023 , 0/038]	[0/01 , 0/016]
S3	[0/042 , 0/095]	[0/015 , 0/032]	[0/002 , 0/004]	[0/01 , 0/015]	[0/006 , 0/011]	[0/025 , 0/044]	[0/008 , 0/017]
S4	[0/049 , 0/108]	[0/019 , 0/036]	[0/002 , 0/004]	[0/006 , 0/014]	[0/006 , 0/011]	[0/028 , 0/042]	[0/011 , 0/018]
	C1	C2	C3	D1	D2	D3	D4
S1	[0/025 , 0/047]	[0/014 , 0/02]	[0/002 , 0/004]	[0/1 , 0/175]	[0/042 , 0/052]	[0/177 , 0/261]	[0/046 , 0/071]
S2	[0/049 , 0/069]	[0/022 , 0/029]	[0/005 , 0/007]	[0/132 , 0/207]	[0/038 , 0/051]	[0/187 , 0/29]	[0/042 , 0/065]
S3	[0/04 , 0/067]	[0/013 , 0/027]	[0/003 , 0/005]	[0/136 , 0/218]	[0/025 , 0/044]	[0/176 , 0/29]	[0/025 , 0/06]
S4	[0/039 , 0/068]	[0/019 , 0/029]	[0/002 , 0/005]	[0/087 , 0/183]	[0/024 , 0/046]	[0/159 , 0/289]	[0/041 , 0/068]

Determination of Positive and Negative Ideals

In this section, the process of determining positive and negative ideals is discussed. The positive ideal is defined as the maximum upper bound value for each criterion's column in the weighted matrix, as per equations 3-18 and 3-17. Conversely, the negative ideal is defined as the minimum lower bound value for each criterion's column in the weighted matrix. The positive and negative ideals are detailed in Table 4-22.

Table 4-22: Positive and Negative Ideals.

	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3	B4
Positive Ideals	[0/133 , 0/133]	[0/036 , 0/036]	[0/004 , 0/004]	[0/015 , 0/015]	[0/012 , 0/012]	[0/044 , 0/044]	[0/018 , 0/018]
Negative Ideals	[0/042 , 0/042]	[0/015 , 0/015]	[0/001 , 0/001]	[0/006 , 0/006]	[0/004 , 0/004]	[0/018 , 0/018]	[0/006 , 0/006]
	C1	C2	C3	D1	D2	D3	D4
Positive Ideals	[0/069 , 0/069]	[0/029 , 0/029]	[0/007 , 0/007]	[0/218 , 0/218]	[0/052 , 0/052]	[0/29 , 0/29]	[0/071 , 0/071]
Negative Ideals	[0/025 , 0/025]	[0/013 , 0/013]	[0/002 , 0/002]	[0/087 , 0/087]	[0/024 , 0/024]	[0/159 , 0/159]	[0/025 , 0/025]

Distance from Positive and Negative Ideals

In this section, the distances of options in the weighted matrix from the positive and negative ideals are determined using equations 3-20 and 3-19. As an example, for the first option, we have:

$$d_1^+ = \{(0.048 - 0.133)^2 + (0.021 - 0.036)^2 + (0.001 - 0.004)^2 + (0.006 - 0.015)^2 + \dots\}^{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.209$$

$$d_1^- = \{(0.048 - 0.042)^2 + (0.021 - 0.015)^2 + (0.001 - 0.001)^2 + (0.006 - 0.006)^2 + \dots\}^{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.161$$

Table 4-23: Distance from Positive and Negative Ideals.

Table 4-23: The Weighted Rough TOPSIS Matrix

d-	D+	
0/161	0/209	S1
0/230	0/148	S2
0/212	0/186	S3
0/192	0/216	S4

Determination of Final Scores and Ranking of Options

In this section, the final score for each option is calculated based on equation 3-16. Subsequently, the final ranking is established using the following formulas:

$$CL_{S1} = 0.161 / (0.161 + 0.209) = 0.435$$

$$CL_{S2} = 0.23 / (0.23 + 0.148) = 0.609$$

$$CL_{S3} = 0.212 / (0.212 + 0.186) = 0.532$$

$$CL_{S4} = 0.192 / (0.192 + 0.216) = 0.471$$

According to the results, Caspian (S2) has obtained the first rank, Pars Charkhesh Asia (S3) secures the second rank, Digi Recycling (S4) achieves the third rank, and Rino (S1) attains the fourth rank.

Results of the Rough WASPAS Method:

In the realm of reverse logistics, where the process involves the planning, implementation, and control of materials from their point of consumption to origin for value recapturing or proper disposal, making informed decisions is paramount. Particularly when forming strategic alliances, selecting the right suppliers is a pivotal step. To ensure robustness in our decision-making, we employed both the Rough TOPSIS and Rough Waspas methods, both of which are grounded in multi-criteria decision-making and utilize rough set theory to deal with uncertainties and incomplete information frequently encountered in real-world scenarios.

The Rough TOPSIS method functions by identifying an ideal and an anti-ideal solution, subsequently comparing each supplier alternative with these reference points. The proximity of each supplier to the ideal solution, juxtaposed with its distance from the anti-ideal solution, ascertains its ranking. Conversely, Rough Waspas amalgamates the features of the weighted sum model (WSM) and the weighted product model (WPM), offering a comprehensive ranking approach. The rationale behind integrating both these methods is multifold. Firstly, employing multiple methods to rank suppliers mitigates the risk of bias stemming from the idiosyncrasies of a single method, bolstering the confidence in the obtained results. Secondly, given the complexities of reverse logistics and the significance of strategic alliances, a more comprehensive and nuanced decision-making technique is invaluable. By juxtaposing the rankings generated by both Rough TOPSIS and Rough Waspas, we aim to affirm the reliability of our decisions, ensuring that no critical factors are overlooked.

To validate the results of the Rough TOPSIS method, Rough WASPAS is employed for re-ranking the suppliers. The steps of this method are outlined below:

A. Formation of the Decision Matrix:

The decision matrix in this method is the same as the decision matrix in the Rough TOPSIS method, as presented in Table 4-19.

B. Normalization of the Decision Matrix:

Normalization in this method follows the same normalization procedure as in the Rough TOPSIS method, using equations 3-22 and 3-23, as depicted in Table 4-20.

C. Determination of Weighted Sum Model and Weighted Product Model Values:

In the third step, using equations 3-24 and 3-25, the values of the Weighted Sum Model (WSM) (Q) and the Weighted Product Model (WPM) (P) are calculated, as provided in Table 4-24.

Table 4-22 Values of WSM and WPM

	Q	P
A1	[0/511 , 0/82]	[0/496 , 0/811]
A2	[0/654 , 0/972]	[0/651 , 0/972]
A3	[0/526 , 0/928]	[0/511 , 0/921]
A4	[0/495 , 0/923]	[0/486 , 0/92]
Σ	[2/187 , 3/643]	[2/145 , 3/624]

Determining the Final Score and Ranking of Options

In the fourth step, the score of each option is calculated using equation 3-26. However, before that, the value of λ is calculated based on equation 3-27, which is provided in Table 4-23. For example, the value of λ is calculated as follows:

$$\lambda = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m P_i}{\sum_{i=1}^m P_i + \sum_{i=1}^m Q_i} = \frac{[3.624 , 2.145]}{[3.624 , 2.145] + [3.643 , 2.187]} = [0.837 , 0.295]$$

How to calculate it ?

This method works by considering the bounds or limits of the numerator and the denominator. Specifically, to obtain the lower bound of the result, the smallest value (lower limit) of the numerator is divided by the largest value (upper limit) of the denominator. Conversely, to obtain the upper bound of the result, the largest value (upper limit) of the numerator is divided by the smallest value (lower limit) of the denominator. In essence, this method captures the extremes to provide a range that encompasses all potential outcomes.

Calculating a Grey Numbers :

Grey numbers offer a way to represent and compute with uncertain numbers. In grey system theory, a grey number is typically presented as an interval, capturing the range of uncertainty for that number.

Steps:

1. Identify the grey number for the numerator, which includes its lower and upper limits.
2. Identify the grey number for the denominator, which also consists of its lower and upper limits.
3. To determine the lower bound of the resulting fraction (λ_{lower}):
 - Divide the lower limit of the numerator's grey number by the upper limit of the denominator's grey number.
4. To determine the upper bound of the resulting fraction (λ_{upper}):
 - Divide the upper limit of the numerator's grey number by the lower limit of the denominator's grey number.

Numerator's Grey Number: ([3.624 , 2.145])

Denominator's Grey Number: ([3.624+3.643 , 2.145+2.187]) which becomes ([7.267 , 4.332])

Using the principles of grey numbers:

$$1. (\lambda_{lower} = \frac{3.624}{4.332}) = 0.8366 \text{ (rounded to 4 decimal places)}$$

$$2. (\lambda_{upper} = \frac{2.145}{7.267}) = 0.2952 \text{ (rounded to 4 decimal places)}$$

Thus, the range for the fraction, represented as a grey number, is ([0.2952 , 0.8366]), capturing both the minimum and maximum possible values.

Next, the final score of the options is calculated as:

$$S_1 = [0.837 , 0.295] \times [0.82 , 0.511] + (1 - [0.837 , 0.295]) \times [0.811 , 0.496] = [1.258 , 0.232]$$

For other options, calculations are also performed, the results of which are provided in Table 4-23. Based on this, Caspian (S2) has achieved the first rank. Pars Charkhesh Asia (S3) is in second place, Digi Recycling (S4) is in third place, and Rino (S1) is also in third place.

Table 4-23 Score of Each Option and Their Ranking

Code	Option Name	Rough Score	Score Definitive	Rank
S1	Rino	[0.232 , 1.258]	0.745	4
S2	Caspian	[0.3 , 1.498]	0.899	1
S3	Pars Charkhesh Asia	[0.239 , 1.425]	0.832	2
S4	Digi Recycling	[0.225 , 1.42]	0.823	3

The table delineates the conclusive scores and placements of the options examined in the study. Every option underwent a meticulous assessment, resulting in an initial approximation and a final, precise score, which ultimately determined their overall ranking. The findings indicate that Caspian emerged as the preeminent selection, succeeded by Pars Charkhesh Asia, Digi Recycling, and Rino, in that order. Such results furnish a delineated and hierarchized roster of suppliers for strategic collaboration in reverse logistics within the electronics sector, derived from an exhaustive and methodical evaluative procedure.

Chapter Five
Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusion :

This study embarked on delineating the pivotal factors influencing user preferences in the selection of communication systems within the electronics sector. To this end, an exhaustive review of both national and international literature, alongside previous empirical research, was undertaken to distill fundamental principles and scholarly contributions pertinent to the exclusion of significant variables during bibliographic exploration, spanning four core domains. This groundwork facilitated the development of a questionnaire encompassing 16 determinants deemed influential in shaping consumer selections, which was subsequently administered to a panel of subject-matter experts. These experts were tasked with validating the relevance of each proposed indicator, endorsing the established metrics, and suggesting any potentially overlooked aspects.

Employing a Likert scale ranging from 1 (very low importance) to 5 (very high importance), 25 expert respondents were invited to rate each criterion. The process involved calculating the mean score for each index, with those averaging below a threshold of 3 earmarked for exclusion. This evaluative phase culminated in the dismissal of two indices—'Environmentally Friendly Design Production' and 'Employment Stability'—due to insufficient mean scores, thereby consolidating a final list of 14 indices.

Subsequent analytical phases leveraged the Analytic Network Process (ANP) methodology to assign weights to the retained criteria, facilitated by the utilization of a limit supermatrix to derive their final weights. The outcomes of this analytical process spotlighted 'Knowledge Management' as the foremost criterion with a weight of 0.2904, followed by 'Risk Sharing' at 0.2184, and 'Quality' at 0.133, indicating their paramount significance.

The concluding phase of the research entailed the application of Rough Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) and Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment (WASPAS) methodologies to rank four shortlisted suppliers. This rigorous comparative analysis revealed Caspian (S2) as the leading supplier, trailed by Pars Charkhesh Asia (S3), Digi Recycling (S4), and Rino (S1), in descending order of preference.

This comprehensive inquiry, underpinned by methodical evaluation and advanced multi-criteria decision-making tools, offers a nuanced framework for assessing supplier options in the electronics industry's communication systems domain, thereby informing strategic selection decisions.

Descriptive Analysis Results

Gender Distribution :

The gender distribution among the participants, as gleaned from the descriptive statistics of the study, indicates a predominant male representation, accounting for 76% of the total respondents.

Educational Background :

Analyzing the educational qualifications of the respondents reveals a diverse academic landscape. Approximately 32% of participants hold a Bachelor's degree, a significant 56% possess a Master's degree, and the remaining 12% have earned Doctoral degrees. This distribution underscores the high level of educational attainment, with a majority holding Master's degrees.

Professional Experience :

The analysis emphasizes work experience as a crucial determinant in the evaluative rigor of the respondents. A substantial 52% of participants boast 10-15 years of professional experience, highlighting the reliance on seasoned judgment in data analysis and decision-making processes.

Age Demographics :

The age-related statistics reveal that a significant portion of the respondents, 48%, falls within the 30-40 age bracket. This is followed by 28% in the 40-50 age range, and 24% are aged above 50 years, showcasing a broad spectrum of age groups among the study participants.

Conceptual Framework Presentation

The research conceptual model is illustrated in Table 5-1, synthesizing the categories, concepts, and components delineated in preceding chapters, offering a comprehensive visual representation of the study's theoretical underpinnings.

Table 5-1 The research conceptual model

Research Findings Analysis

This inquiry delves into the determinants influencing the choice of strategic suppliers for reverse logistics, uncovering the pivotal role of knowledge management. With a significant weight of 0.29, knowledge management emerges as a critical factor. The evolving dynamics of market competition and business ecosystems have revolutionized product delivery protocols and the communication paradigms between purchasers and suppliers. A profound understanding of supplier relationships, predicated on effective knowledge management, is indispensable for optimizing organizational supply chain decisions. Suppliers wield substantial influence over a firm's fiscal outcomes and its operational and strategic efficacy,

underscoring the imperative for astute management of supplier interactions and leveraging the informational and knowledge-based assets they offer.

Risk sharing, attributed a weight of 0.21, stands out as another influential factor. Amidst the uncertainties pervading global supply chain optimization, the capacity to mitigate risks through strategic contractual arrangements—facilitating equitable risk distribution—becomes paramount. The design of supply agreements, incorporating mechanisms for price adaptability and accountability for deviations from agreed procurement volumes, is crucial for minimizing the adverse impacts of demand and cost volatilities.

Quality, assigned a weight of 0.13, is recognized as a third consequential factor. The emphasis on quality transcends the product dimension, encompassing the processes and services associated with procurement. The pursuit of supplier partnerships is predicated not only on product excellence but also on the assurance of quality in pricing, packaging, and delivery facets. The interconnectedness of product, process, and service quality is such that any deficiency in one area could significantly diminish the prospects for ongoing buyer-supplier collaborations, highlighting the integral role of quality assurance in sustaining and nurturing supplier relationships.

Practical Implementation Recommendations:

Risk Sharing as a Core Principle: It is crucial for procurement managers to integrate risk sharing into the supply chain's structure and management. Establishing agreements that accommodate precise demand forecasts and stable procurement costs can mitigate the impacts of demand and price fluctuations, creating a balanced incentive system for both buyers and suppliers.

Sustainability-Focused Contracts: Crafting risk-sharing contracts with a lens on sustainability—addressing social, economic, and environmental issues—is highly recommended to align supply chain practices with broader sustainability goals.

Partnering with Environmentally Conscious Suppliers: Selecting suppliers who prioritize environmental stewardship and utilize eco-friendly materials and processes is advisable for fostering durable, sustainable partnerships.

Information Technology for Enhanced Coordination: Leveraging information technology can synchronize production, inventory, customer data, and supplier activities, optimizing the delivery process to meet efficiency and quality standards.

Production Cost Management: Effective management of production costs can lower overall expenses, making suppliers that adhere to these principles more attractive.

Supplier Relationship Management Implementation: Establishing robust supplier relationship management is essential. Aligning with suppliers who view their relationship with the company as mutually beneficial is crucial for maintaining engagement.

Adapting New Technologies for Organizational Flexibility: Adopting innovative technologies and processes can increase an organization's adaptability to changes in the environment, challenges related to quality, cost, and reliability of deliveries, thus boosting competitiveness.

Future Research Directions for Thesis Enhancement

In the dynamic field of reverse logistics, the selection of strategic suppliers is a critical area ripe for extensive research. Future studies should consider the following multifaceted directions to build upon the current knowledge base and address emerging challenges:

Integration with Machine Learning Algorithms: Investigate the integration of machine learning algorithms to automate the evaluation process, potentially enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of supplier selection in reverse logistics under uncertainty.

Environmental and Social Sustainability Models: There's a pressing need to explore how sustainability considerations, encompassing environmental and social factors, influence reverse logistics supplier selection. Developing comprehensive sustainability assessment models that integrate these criteria can help organizations align with global sustainability objectives and meet evolving consumer expectations.

Economic Implications of Supplier Relationships: Delve into the economic dynamics of maintaining long-term versus short-term relationships with suppliers in the context of reverse logistics. Future analyses could shed light on the cost-benefit aspects of such partnerships, exploring the potential for cost savings, efficiency improvements, and the mitigation of risks.

Cross-Industry Comparative Analysis: Conducting studies across various industries can reveal unique challenges and best practices in reverse logistics supplier selection, offering insights into industry-specific strategies and generalizable principles.

Regulatory Impact Studies: With the regulatory environment for reverse logistics continually evolving, future research should assess how regulatory changes influence strategic decisions and supplier selection criteria, especially in tightly regulated sectors.

Collaboration Models and Stakeholder Engagement: Investigating collaborative models that include customers, suppliers, and regulatory bodies can offer insights into enhancing supply chain resilience and sustainability through effective stakeholder engagement.

Advanced Quantitative Models: The application of sophisticated quantitative models and simulation techniques to predict the impacts of supplier selection decisions on reverse logistics performance could provide decision-makers with valuable predictive insights.

Innovative Practices Case Studies: Analyzing companies that have successfully implemented cutting-edge reverse logistics and supplier selection strategies could serve as a practical reference for industry peers.

Corporate Strategy Integration: Explore how reverse logistics can be more effectively incorporated into the broader corporate strategy and business models, aiming to enhance competitiveness and sustainability.

Educational and Training Program Development : Assess the educational and skill development needs within organizations for improved management of reverse logistics and supplier selection, proposing targeted training programs to bridge identified gaps.

Additionally, the application and comparison of diverse multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methodologies can significantly enhance the strategic selection of reverse logistics suppliers. By accommodating a wide array of data environments and modeling techniques—from certainty and fuzzy logic to neutrosophic sets and rough set theory—research can provide a more adaptable and comprehensive approach to supplier evaluation under varying degrees of uncertainty. Employing advanced data analytics,

such as machine learning and data mining, within these methodologies can uncover deeper insights, facilitating more informed and effective decision-making processes.

Through these expanded research directions, future studies can offer groundbreaking insights and methodologies, driving forward the capabilities and understanding of reverse logistics supplier selection to meet the challenges of modern supply chains.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this thesis, titled "Evaluating and Selecting Strategic Alliance Suppliers in Reverse Logistics Using the ANP-TOPSIS Hybrid Method in a Rough Uncertainty Environment," represents a comprehensive exploration into optimizing supplier selection processes within the sphere of reverse logistics. Through meticulous research and analysis, this study has established a novel framework that synergizes the Analytic Network Process (ANP) with the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), refined further by incorporating rough set theory to adeptly navigate the inherent uncertainties of the reverse logistics domain.

The significance of this research lies not only in its contribution to the academic discourse on supply chain management and reverse logistics but also in its practical implications for industry professionals seeking to enhance operational efficiencies and sustainability. By applying this hybrid methodological approach, organizations are equipped with a robust tool for making informed decisions in the selection of strategic alliance suppliers, thus fostering a more resilient and environmentally responsible supply chain network.

Moreover, the case study centered on electronic waste recycling companies elucidates the practical applicability of the proposed framework, demonstrating its potential to significantly impact operational performance and sustainability practices across industries engaged in reverse logistics activities.

As this research endeavor reaches its culmination, it is imperative to acknowledge the scope for further investigation and development within this field. The dynamic nature of reverse logistics, coupled with the ever-evolving challenges of global supply chains, calls for continuous exploration and refinement of methodologies to stay abreast of industry needs and sustainability goals. Future research may delve into the integration of emerging technologies, the exploration of cross-industry applications, and the assessment of long-term environmental impacts, thereby enriching the discourse and practice of reverse logistics and supplier selection.

This thesis is presented in the hope that it will serve as a foundational reference for both scholars and practitioners aiming to navigate the complexities of supplier selection in reverse logistics, contributing to the advancement of knowledge and the promotion of sustainable practices within the global supply chain landscape.

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